

Université Grenoble Alpes

École doctorale STEP :
Sciences de la Terre, de l'environnement et des
planètes

Habilitation à diriger des recherches

Roberto GRILLI

Institut des Géosciences de l'Environnement (IGE)

Development of optical absorption sensors for geochemistry and earth sciences applications

23 September 2024

Membres du Jury :

M. Lukas EMMENEGGER (Rapporteur)

Mme. Nathalie HURET (Rapporteur)

Mme. Barbara STENNI (Rapporteur)

M. Didier VOISIN (Examineur)

M. Gilles REVERDIN (Examineur)

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	My scientific journey	1
1.2	Between fundamental and applied sciences: not an easy task	4
1.3	My Curriculum Vitae	6
1.4	Outline of my HDR thesis	15
2	2. Absorption spectroscopy techniques	17
2.1	The basics of molecular absorption spectroscopy	17
2.2	Direct absorption, multipass cells, or optical cavities?	18
2.3	Different sources, different wavelength regions, different techniques	22
3	Applications to dissolved gas measurements	25
3.1	Introduction	25
3.2	<i>In situ</i> dissolved gases measurements: CH ₄ , δ ¹³ CH ₄ and C ₂ H ₆	27
3.2.1	The first applications of the SubOcean instrument for high-resolution mapping of dissolved methane	29
3.2.2	More recent field campaigns with the SubOcean probe and the technology transfer	33
3.3	<i>In situ</i> water isotope measurements: δD, δ ¹⁸ O and δ ¹⁷ O of H ₂ O	35
3.3.1	Introduction and scientific motivation	35
3.3.2	The Subsea water isotope sensor	36
3.3.3	Field applications	40
3.4	Conclusion and perspectives	41
4	Applications to atmospheric chemistry	43
4.1	The Oxidative capacity at polar regions	43
4.2	The IBB-CEAS instrument for NO _x , CHOCHO and IO measurements	45
4.3	First applications of the IBB-CEAS instruments for understanding the NO _x chemistry at polar regions	46
4.3.1	New Estimation of the NO _x Snow-Sources on the Antarctic Plateau	46
4.3.2	Summer variability of the atmospheric NO ₂ :NO ratio at Dome C	49
4.3.3	Application of the IBB-CEAS instrument for understanding the chemistry in urban areas	52
4.3.4	Conversion of one of the two IBB-CEAS systems into an open-path analyzer	53
4.4	The attempt to LP-DOAS measurements for halogen oxide radicals	55
4.5	Conclusion and perspectives	58

5 Applications to ice core sciences	61
5.1 Atmospheric CO ₂ in ice cores to study carbon cycle - climate feedback	61
5.2 Development of a CO ₂ and δ ¹³ CO ₂ spectrometer	63
5.3 Development of a new dry extraction method	66
5.4 Conclusion and perspectives	71
6 General conclusion and perspectives	75
6.1 Strategy, objective, and feasibility	75
6.2 Research plan	79
Bibliography	83

Introduction

Contents

1.1	My scientific journey	1
1.2	Between fundamental and applied sciences: not an easy task	4
1.3	My Curriculum Vitae	6
1.4	Outline of my HDR thesis	15

1.1 My scientific journey

After middle school, I already knew very well what I wanted to do later and what I wanted to study. I have always been very interested in knowing how everything works, and a high school specialized in chemistry seemed to me the best option to focus on scientific subjects, which I was more comfortable with than literary ones. After the specialization, I was also confident that I wanted to continue my studies. I enjoyed chemistry very much: with a good knowledge of chemistry, I felt that most of the things around us could be understood and explained. In 2000, I applied for a degree in chemistry at the University of Perugia and I truly enjoyed studying physical, organic and analytical chemistry as well as the other scientific topics.

For the master, I had to choose between the different type of chemistry. This was a quite hard choice since I was fascinated by all of them, but I had the feeling that organic chemistry could be more easily touchable, I liked the idea of finding a way to build up molecules, but I also liked a lot the use analytical tools to characterize and study them. For those reasons, I decided to do a master's project on the interactions between amphiphilic molecules and DNA. Amphiphilic molecules have both hydrophilic (water-attracting) and hydrophobic (water-repelling) regions, which allow them to self-assemble into various macro-molecular structures, such as micelles, liposomes, and vesicles. These structures can encapsulate DNA, becoming potential vectors from gene delivery into the cells. Characterizing these interactions would allow finding a suitable molecule not only for its transport but also for its release inside the cell. Therefore, not only the interaction should be reversible, but the assembly should not damage the DNA structure. I was very excited and enthusiastic about this project because it allowed me to couple engineering (at molecular scale), and analytical skills while working on a tangible application for medical and biology sciences. Although it seems far from what I am currently doing, there is actually

quite a lot in common, and since then I knew that I liked the idea of playing with analytical instrumentation and being at the interface between different disciplines.

During the master's degree, I had the opportunity to do a three-month Erasmus project at the School of Chemistry in the University of Bristol in UK. This experience was very stimulating both in terms of life experience, opening up to other cultures, and from the scientific point of view. Although I was a bit scared of living in another country, it allowed me to broaden further up my vision of what I could do, and I was attracted by the laser spectroscopy techniques and their applications to trace gas detection in environmental sciences. What stimulated me strongly about this topic was the idea of building analytical tools from scratch, which required engineering skills, and use them for understanding climate evolution, which, at the time, was already a topic of serious concern to me.

In 2006, I then decided to start a PhD at the University of Bristol supervised by Prof. Andrew Orr-Ewing on the development of new methods for trace gas detection using optical spectroscopy. It was challenging for me since I needed to strengthen my background in laser physics and optical spectroscopy, but Andrew showed a lot of trust in me, and thanks to him, his group, and to other professors and scientists that I met during this PhD journey, I could foster my knowledge in this subject and realize how much I liked it. Being able to build, characterize, optimize, and validate a completely new and innovative tool with key applications in environmental sciences was for me an extremely motivating objective.

At the end of my PhD, at the beginning of 2010, I moved to Grenoble in France with the aim of getting closer to environmental applications. The goal of my first post-doc was perfect for this: build a new optical spectrometer for measuring halogen oxide radicals (IO and BrO) in the atmosphere and perform measurements in Antarctica! This was a joint project between the LIPhy (Laboratoire Interdisciplinaire de Physique) and the IGE (Institut de Geosciences de l'Environnement, Former LGGE). At LIPhy I had the opportunity to work in the [LAME \(LASers, MOlecules and Environment\)](#) group, with very strong expertise in the development of high-sensitive optical techniques, and the implication of IGE allowed me to build a close and strong relationship with what was for me the most interesting application for those optical methods. During the Austral summer of 2012-2013, I had the opportunity to take the developed instrument to the Dumont D'Urville (DDU) station in Antarctica. This was the first time that I could take an optical instrument from its conception, building, and development to the final field campaign! And not a whatso-ever campaign, but a field trip to the most remote country, the white giant 15,000 km away from France, of which the ice allowed us to reconstruct the last 800,000 years of climate. Atmospheric chemistry in such a pristine and remote environment is extremely interesting for understanding the fundamental chemical and photochemical processes at work in an area with very limited anthropogenic influences, and allows for a better interpretation of the atmospheric signal recorded in ice cores.

With my second Post-doc in a collaboration between the same two laboratories, I moved further closer to ice core science, and I participated in the ambitious project

of building an *in situ* drilling probe for analyzing the composition of the water and air bubbles trapped in the ice while drilling down the ice sheet. The ice core community is willing to find ice older than 1 million years, and drilling the 3,000 m of ice sheet in Antarctica with the current drilling equipment takes at least four years of work. It was too long and too risky to start the drilling and realise many years later that it was perhaps not the best location to find very old ice. This is where the idea of the SubGlaciator probe came in: this probe, unique in its kind, couples ice core drilling and *in situ* analysis and was designed for continuously drilling the ice sheet and reaching bedrock in a single summer season. With an embedded optical spectrometer it would provide real-time data, allowing us to evaluate the depth-to-age relationship for the studied site. With a team of 20 engineers, we developed this very challenging probe: A giant instrument 12 m long, and 480 kg of weight, that was coupling mechanical and thermal drilling, sample handling (air bubble extraction), and composition analysis (CH_4 and δD of H_2O) using an optical spectrometer. After three years of work, during the Austral summer of 2016/2017, the tool was ready for the first test campaign. Although the working principle was demonstrated in the field, the test campaign was difficult due to a task that was unfortunately underestimated by the project: sealing the porous firn layer (the first 120 m of ice). For continuous drilling down to a depth of 3,000 m, silicone oil had to be injected into the borehole to prevent the hole from closing up, and by making a circulation of the silicon oil, ice chips produced by the drilling head could be recovered at the surface. Afterward, the period of the pandemic did not facilitate further tests in the field and added further delay on the validation of this novel tool. Meanwhile, the ice core community managed to better constrain the parameters that allowed to predict the depth-to-age relationship at a given site: geothermal heat from the bedrock, snow accumulation, and glacier dynamics. According to those parameters, the "Little Dome-C" site, 40 km away from the station of Concordia, was selected as a site with a strong potential for possessing preserved ice samples older than 1 Myrs, and in the austral summer of 2021/2021 the new drilling mission called [Beyond-EPICA Oldest Ice](#) started. The team reached 1836 m of depth during the last campaign (2023/2024) and the oldest ice (>800,000 years), contained in the last 300 m below 2400 m of depth, should not be too far. I said "should" because the relationship between depth and age is not linear, and it's difficult to predict, from the isotopic analysis of water performed directly in the field, what age we should expect at the bedrock. According to F. Parrenin and the PhD student working with him, A. Chung, it could be very old ice, but it could also be ice even younger than the one from the EPICA drilling. So there will be a lot of suspense I guess in the coming drilling season!

During the two post-docs, I wanted to apply for a position as a research fellow at the CNRS, but the science I wanted to carry out could be considered "too applied" for a physics and laser spectroscopy section, and "too fundamental/instrumental" for an environmental science section. It was no easy to find a way to sit at the interface between the physical and environmental sciences. The crucial question was: in which section should I apply? In which laboratory would I like to carry out

Figure 1.1: My scientific journey, from the master's degree to a research scientist

my research? Being in a physical laboratory would probably be more comfortable for pursuing instrumental developments since I could interact on a daily basis with experts in optical instrumentation. However, joining a geoscience laboratory would enable me to get closer and create scientific collaborations with scientists working in the environmental sciences. This is what I think would make a real difference to the position I was aiming for. On the other hand, this option would require a lot more work in the first few years, as I would have to set up from scratch a laboratory equipped with the necessary facilities for optical developments.

In 2015 I was recruited as a scientific researcher in section 19 : "Earth system: surface envelopes" with a project entitled "Coupling climate-geochemistry via innovative laser methods: at the interface between environmental sciences and optics", and I joined the ICE3 (Ice Cores, Climate, Chemistry) research team at IGE. My idea was to build novel spectroscopy tools and use them in the field of atmospheric chemistry, ice core science et aquatic systems for both laboratory and field measurements. It is a real challenge but also extremely exciting!

1.2 Between fundamental and applied sciences: not an easy task

In research, and not only in scientific areas, people are used to acquire deep expertises on a specific topic and this is possible only by narrowing the concerned field of study. Therefore, the most common way of conducting research projects at the interface between different areas is to set up a collaboration, where experts in different areas work together to create something new and challenging. This usually

works and provides exciting science, but it often works for a specific project at a given time, making more difficult to secure long-term cooperation.

Here, a concrete example for the development of a new optical spectrometer for geoscience applications. The instrumental development requires physics and engineering skills and is therefore led by scientists in a physics/engineering laboratory. Applications such as studying the atmospheric chemistry of certain species, understanding past climate, or studying the metabolism of aquatic environments require skills that the scientists who developed the tools do not possess. During my first post-doc, I developed this frequency-comb-based cavity-enhanced absorption spectrometer for measuring halogen oxide radicals in the atmosphere, and once it was time to decide who would take the instrument in the field, there were not many options: if we wanted to ensure a successful operation of the instrument in the field, was myself who developed the instrument the best person to operate it in the field. To bring a development up to a level where a non-expert can easily operate it is not always simple, and requires a lot of further work of the scientists in the laboratory that lead the development to make the instrument "press button" and "easy to use". Those further efforts need to find the interest of the developers, the required funding, and the prospective for either a commercialization or a technological transfer. Therefore, for a long-term commitment to the deployment and use of novel cutting-edge tools in specific research areas one needs to bring this expertise to the final users, and this is my role at IGE: work closely to geoscientists, build up collaborations with them and ensure that those novel developments will be available for producing outstanding research.

As it has been said it may seem a simple task, but I can ensure that it is not that easy, for the main reason I mentioned above: we are tempted to acquire more and more expertise in a given field of research. In my case what it would be? If it is the development and engineering of optical spectrometers then what is the point of doing it in a geosciences laboratory? If it is becoming an expert in environmental sciences I would then need to narrow down the research applications, which would represent a "defeat" with respect to the objectives I gave myself when I applied for the CNRS position.

Working at the interface between two disciplines and having requests covering different research topics requires a certain "self-censorship" in the way the work is pursued. I am particularly careful not to do too many different developments at the same time, to always make sure that optical developments are at the center of my research activities, and to think about how a certain development could be readapted to different research topics. Finally, a hard task consists of selecting the bibliography to read and the conferences to attend. I have to admit that, because of the broad research field I am covering, I have a difficult time to stay updated regarding the literature. I would then need to select what publications to read, and most of the time I have a natural selection done by the urgency of a certain readings with respect to others. Regarding conferences, I usually prefer small and well-focused conferences, but from time to time, I opt for large international conferences (like the EGU for example) which enable me to cover the whole range of geoscientific

applications in a single venue.

1.3 My Curriculum Vitae

Personal web page: <https://www.ige-grenoble.fr/-Grilli-Roberto-> ORCID Number: 0000-0001-5636-264X

EDUCATION

[2010] PhD at the School of Chemistry, University of Bristol (UK). Supervisor Prof. A. Orr-Ewing

[2000 - 2006] Chemistry Degree, University of Perugia (Italy)

PREVIOUS RESEARCH ACTIVITIES

[2012 - 2015] Postdoc at LIPhy, Université Grenoble Alpes – Grenoble (France)

[2010 - 2012] Postdoc at IGE and LIPhy, Université Grenoble Alpes – Grenoble (France)

[2006] Research Activity at the Centre of Excellence on Nanostructured Innovative Material for Biochemical and Biomedical Physical Applications (CEMIN), University of Perugia (Italy)

SUPERVISING

Since 2010 I supervised 3 PhD students, 5 engineers and co-supervised 4 others and supervised 4 M1 and 2 M2 internships.

[2023-...] Co-supervision of research engineer L. Richard on the development of a new optical spectrometer for measuring the isotopologues of CO in ice core. (*10% of supervision, 90% from LIPhy*).

[2023] One-month summer Internship of F. Pastierovic from the Comenius University Bratislava (Slovakia) on the advances on IBBCEAS instruments for NO₂, IO and CHOCHO detection. (*100% of supervision*).

[2023-...] Supervision of the apprentice Y. Yahiaoui on the development of the optical spectrometer for measuring CO₂ and $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ in ice core and the ice core extraction technique (*30% supervising, 30% G. Teste, 30% F. Michel*).

[2023-...] Supervision of research engineer J. Witwicky for the deployment of the

SWIS instrument at Fimbul Ice Shelf in Antarctica. (*50% of supervision, 50% from A. Wohleber*).

[2023-...] Supervision of research engineer F. Michel for continuing the development of a new optical spectrometer for measuring CO₂ and $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ in ice core (*80% of supervision, 20% from LIPhy*).

[2022- ...] Supervision of engineer E. Barraux in partnership with the company A2 Photonic Sensors on the commercialization of the sensors for measuring dissolved gas. (*25% of supervision, 75% from A2 Photonic Sensors*).

[2022] Supervision of the M1 internship (3 months) of E. Gros on the characterization of a system for measuring sulfur isotopes in Ice Core (*75% of supervision, 25% from S. Dasari*).

[2022] Supervision of the M1 internship (3 months) of N. Steininger on the development of the optical spectrometer for measuring CO₂ and $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ in ice core (*50% of supervision, 50% from E. Negre*).

[2021-...] PhD thesis of A. Wohleber on the development and first applications of the Subsea water isotope sensors (SWIS) (*100% of supervision*).

[2021-2023] Supervision of research engineer E. Negre on the project IsoCarb for developing a new optical spectrometer for measuring CO₂ and $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ in ice core (*80% of supervision, 20% from LIPhy*).

[2021] Supervision of the M2 internship (6 months) of S. Arioli on the LP-DOAS measurement of halogenated radicals (*75% of supervision, 25% from LIPhy*).

[2021] Supervision of the M2 internship (5 months) of A. Wohleber on the characterization of the new sensors for the in situ measurement of water isotopes in the ocean (*50% of supervision, 50% from C. Blouzon*).

[2020] Co-supervision of the M1 internship (3 months) of M. Schwarz on LP-DOAS measurement of halogenated radicals (main supervisor G. Méjean, LIPHy) (*50% of supervision*).

[2018-2021] Supervision of research engineer C. Blouzon on the ANR SWIS for developing a new sensor for the in situ measurement of water isotopes in the ocean (*100% of supervision*).

[2018-2021] PhD thesis of A. Barbero on atmospheric chemistry in polar regions. After the PhD Albane obtained a post-doctoral position in CHIANTI research group at IGE (*50% of supervising, 50% J. Savarino*).

[2018] Co-supervision of the engineer J. Morfin, hired at IGE on the SubGlacior sampling line (*50% of supervision*).

[2017-2018] Supervision of the research engineer C. Blouzon on the development of the IBBCEAS instruments for the atmospheric measurement of NO_x (*100% of supervision*).

[2016] I contributed to the supervision of engineer C. Dupraz on the measurement of CO₂ in ice cores. Clara worked with J. Shin on the extraction techniques and their optimization (*10% of supervision*).

[2016] Supervision of the M1 internship DUT Mesures Physiques (3 months) of V. Ledoux on the measurement of dissolved gases (*100% of supervision*).

[2015-2018] PhD thesis of J. Shin on the evolution of atmospheric CO₂ in ice cores. After the PhD Jinhwa obtained a post-doctoral fellow at the University of Alberta in Canada (*50% of supervision, 50% J. Chappellaz*).

ORGANISATION OF SCIENTIFIC EVENTS

[2021 - ...] Implication in the organization of the AEI (Atelier Expérimentation et Instrumentation) organized by the CSIIT (Commission Spécialisée Instrumentation Innovante Transverse de l'INSU) of which I am a member.

[2020] I was in the scientific committee of Défi 16 of INSU "Instrumentation in extreme environments" at Clermont-Ferrand (January 30-31).

[2019] I contributed to the laboratory's open day and the CNRS 80th anniversary celebrations with an Art & Science show entitled "The sound of the ice".

[2017 - ...] Since 2017 I am coordinating the spectroscopy group at OSUG (Observatoire des Sciences de l'Univers de Grenoble), where we organize thematic meetings.

[2016] Co-organizer of the International Conference FLAIR (Field Laser Applications in Industry and Research) at Aix-les-bains (France). 170 participants.

RESEARCH ADMINISTRATION

[2023 - ...] Coordinator of the ICE3 team at IGE

[2021 - ...] Part of the CSIIT (Commission Spécialisée Instrumentation Innovante Transverse de l'INSU)

TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER TO THE COMPANIES

[2022 - ...] Ongoing technology transfer to A2 Photonic Sensors for commercializing fast dissolved gas sensors.

LIST OF SUBMITTED PUBLICATIONS (*names of students and post-docs supervised)

Legrain E., Capron E., Menviel L., Wohleber A.*, Parrenin F., Teste G., Landais A., Bouchet M., Grilli R., Nehrbass-Ahles C., Silva L., Fischer H., Stocker T. F., « High obliquity favours centennial-scale variations in the carbon cycle. » Submitted to Nature Geosciences, May **2024**.

Strawson I, Faïn X., Bauska T. K., Muschitiello F., Vladimirova D. O., Tetzner D. R., Humby J., Thomas E. R., Liu P., Zhang B., Grilli R., Rhodes R. H., "Pre-industrial Southern Hemisphere biomass burning variability inferred from ice core carbon monoxide records", PNAS, in press. (**2024**).

Wohleber A.*, Blouzon C.*, Witwicky J.*, Ginot G. , Jourdain N. C. , Grilli R., "A membrane inlet laser spectrometer for in situ measurement of triple water isotopologues", submitted to Limnology and Oceanography: Methods, June **2024**.

LIST OF PUBLICATIONS (*names of students and post-docs supervised)

34. Albertin S, Savarino J, Bekki S, Barbero A.*, Grilli R., Fournier Q., Ventrillard I., Caillon N., Law K., « Diurnal variations in oxygen and nitrogen isotopes of atmospheric nitrogen dioxide and nitrate : implications for tracing NOx oxidation pathways and emission sources. » Atmos Chem Phys, 24(2):1361-1388. doi:10.5194/acp-24-1361-2024 (**2024**)

33. Faïn X., Etheridge D.M., Fourteau K., Martinerie P., Trudinger C. M., Rhodes R. H., Chellman N. J., Langenfelds R. L., McConnell J. R., Curran M. A. J., Brook E. J., Blunier T., Teste G., Grilli R., Lemoine A., Sturges W. T., Vanniere B., Freitag J., Chappellaz J., « Southern Hemisphere atmospheric history of carbon monoxide over the late Holocene reconstructed from multiple Antarctic ice archives. » Clim Past., 19, 2287–2311. doi: 10.5194/cp-19-2287-2023 (**2023**)

32. Grilli R., Delsontro T., Garnier J., Jacob F., Némery J., « A novel high-resolution in situ tool for studying carbon biogeochemical processes in aquatic systems : The Lake Aiguebelette case study. » Journal of Geophysical Research : Biogeosciences, 128, e2022JG007200. doi: 10.1029/2022JG007200 (**2023**)

31. A. Barbero*, J. Savarino, R. Grilli, M. M. Frey, C. Blouzon*, D. Helmig,

N. Caillon, « Summer variability of the atmospheric NO₂:NO ratio at Dome C, on the East Antarctic Plateau. » *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 22, 12025–12054, doi: [10.5194/acp-22-12025-2022](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-12025-2022) (2022).

30. Fleurbaey H, Campargue A, Carreira Mendès Da Silva Y, Grilli R, Kassi S, Mondelain D. « Characterization of the H₂O+CO₂ continuum within the infrared transparency windows. » *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, Elsevier, 282, 108119 doi: [10.1016/j.jqsrt.2022.108119](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2022.108119) (2022). [hal-03752050](https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-03752050)

29. Dølven KO, Vierinen J, Grilli R, Triest J, Ferré B. « Response time correction of slow-response sensor data by deconvolution of the growth-law equation. » *Geosci Instrumentation, Methods Data Syst.*, 11(2):293-306, doi: [10.5194/gi-11-293-2022](https://doi.org/10.5194/gi-11-293-2022) (2022).

28. H. Fleurbaey, R. Grilli, D. Mondelain, A. Campargue « Measurements of the water vapor continuum absorption by OFCEAS at 3.50 μm and 2.32 μm » *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.*, 278, 108004, doi: [10.1016/j.jqsrt.2021.108004](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2021.108004) (2022).

27. R. Grilli, Birot, D., Schumacher, M., Paris, J.-D., Blouzon, C.*, Donval, J. P., Guyader, V., Leau, H., Giunta, T., Delmotte, M., Radulescu, V., Balan, S., Greinert, J. and Ruffine, L. « Inter-comparison of the spatial distribution of methane in the water column from seafloor emissions at two sites in the Western Black Sea, using a multi-technique approach », *Front. Earth Sci.*, 9(July), 1–15, doi: [10.3389/feart.2021.626372](https://doi.org/10.3389/feart.2021.626372) (2021).

26. Barbero, A.*, Savarino, J., Grilli, R., Blouzon, C.*, Picard, G., Frey, M. M., Huang, Y. and Caillon, N. : New estimation of the snow-source on the Antarctic Plateau, *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.*, (x), 1–38, doi: [10.1029/2021JD035062](https://doi.org/10.1029/2021JD035062) (2021).

25. H. Fleurbaey, R. Grilli, D. Mondelain, S. Kassi, A. Yachmenev, S. N. Yurchenko, A. Campargue « Electric-quadrupole and magnetic-dipole contributions to the $\nu_2+\nu_3$ band of carbon dioxide near 3.3 μm » *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transf.*, 266, 107558, doi: [10.1016/j.jqsrt.2021.107558](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2021.107558) (2021).

24. C. Nehrbass-Ahles, J. Shin*, J. Schmitt, B. Bereiter, F. Joos, A. Schilt, L. Schmidely, L. Silva, G. Teste, R. Grilli, J. Chappellaz, D. Hodell, H. Fischer, T. F. Stocker « Abrupt CO₂ release to the atmosphere under glacial and early interglacial climate conditions ». *Science* 365(6506), 1000-1005 doi: [10.1126/science.aay8178](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aay8178) (2020).

23. A. Barbero*, C. Blouzon*, J. Savarino, N. Caillon, A. Dommergue, R. Grilli « A compact incoherent broadband cavity-enhanced absorption spectrometer

for trace detection of nitrogen oxides, iodine oxide and glyoxal at levels below parts per billion for field applications ». Under revision in *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques* 13(8), 4317–4331 doi: [10.5194/amt-13-4317-2020](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-13-4317-2020) (2020).

22. J. Shin*, C. Nehrbass-Ahles, R. Grilli, J. Chowdhry Beeman, F. Parrenin, G. Teste, A. Landais, L. Schmidely, Silva, L., J. Schmitt, H. Fischer, T. F. Stocker, J. Chappellaz, « Millennial-scale atmospheric CO₂ variations during the Marine Isotope Stage 6 period (190-135 kyr BP) ». *Climate of the past* doi: [10.5194/cp-16-2203-2020](https://doi.org/10.5194/cp-16-2203-2020) (2020).

21. F. Bärenbold, B. Boehrer, R. Grilli, A. Mugisha, W. von Tümpling, A. Umutoni, M. Schmid, « No increasing risk of a limnic eruption at Lake Kivu : Intercomparison study reveals gas concentrations close to steady state ». *PLOS ONE*, 15(8), e0237836. [10.1371/journal.pone.0237836](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0237836) (2020).

20. R. Grilli, F. Darchambeau, J. Chappellaz, A. Mugisha, J. Triest, A. Umutoni, « Continuous in situ measurement of dissolved methane in Lake Kivu using a membrane inlet laser spectrometer ». *Geoscientific Instrumentation, Methods and Data Systems*, 9(1), 141–151 doi : [10.5194/gi-9-141-2020](https://doi.org/10.5194/gi-9-141-2020) (2020).

19. P. Jansson, J. Triest, R. Grilli, B. Ferré, A. Silyakova, J. Mienert, J. Chappellaz, « High-resolution under-water laser spectrometer sensing provides new insights to methane distribution at an Arctic seepage site ». *Ocean Sci.*, 15, 1055–1069, doi : [10.5194/os-15-1055-2019](https://doi.org/10.5194/os-15-1055-2019) (2019).

18. L. Lechevallier*, R. Grilli, E. Kerstel, D. Romanini, J. Chappellaz, « Simultaneous Detection of C₂H₆, CH₄ and d₁₃C-CH₄ Using Optical Feedback Cavity Enhanced Absorption Spectroscopy in the Mid-Infrared Region : Towards Application for Dissolved Gas Measurements ». *Atmos. Meas. Tech.*, 12, 3101–3109, doi : [10.5194/amt-12-3101-2019](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-12-3101-2019) (2019).

17. R. Grilli, J. Triest, J. Chappellaz, M. Calzas, T. Desbois, P. Jansson, C. Guillerm, B. Ferré, L. Lechevallier*, V. Ledoux*, D. Romanini, « Sub-Ocean : subsea dissolved methane measurements using an embedded laser spectrometer technology ». *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 52, 10543–10551. doi : [10.1021/acs.est.7b06171](https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.est.7b06171) (2018).

16. L. Lechevallier*, S. Vasilchenko, R. Grilli, D. Mondelain, D. Romanini, A. Campargue, « The water vapor self-continuum absorption in the infrared atmospheric windows : New laser measurements near 3.3 μm and 2.0 μm ». *Atmos. Meas. Tech.* 2018, 11, 2159–2171. doi : [10.5194/amt-11-2159-2018](https://doi.org/10.5194/amt-11-2159-2018) (2018).

15. R. Grilli, N. Marrocco, T. Desbois, C. Guillerm, J. Triest, E. Kerstel, D. Romanini, Invited Article : « SUBGLACIOR : An optical analyzer embedded

in an Antarctic ice probe for exploring the past climate », *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 85 (111301), 1–7. doi : [10.1063/1.4901018](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4901018) (2014).

14. O Alemany, J. Chappellaz, J. Triest, M. Calzas, O. Cattani, J.F. Chemin, Q. Desbois, T. Desbois, R. Duphil, S. Falourd, R. Grilli, C. Guillerme, E. Kerstel, B. Laurent, E. Lefebvre, N. Marocco, O. Pascual, L. Piard, P. Possenti, D. Romanini, V. Thiebaut, R. Yamani, « The SUBGLACIOR drilling probe : concept and design », *Annals of Glaciology*, 55(68), 233–242. doi : [10.3189/2014AoG68A026](https://doi.org/10.3189/2014AoG68A026) (2014).

13. A. Chadi, G. Méjean, R. Grilli, D. Romanini, « Piezoelectric mirror actuator with more than 100 kHz bandwidth using standard components », *Review of Scientific Instruments*, 84, 056112 doi : [10.1002/grl.50154](https://doi.org/10.1002/grl.50154) (2013).

12. R. Grilli, M. Legrand, A. Kukui, G. Méjean, S. Preunkert, D. Romanini, « First investigations of IO, BrO, and NO₂ summer atmospheric levels at a coastal East Antarctic site using mode-locked cavity enhanced absorption spectroscopy ». *Geophysical Research Letters* 40, 1-6. doi : [10.1002/grl.50154](https://doi.org/10.1002/grl.50154) (2013).

11. R. Grilli, G. Méjean, S. Kassi, I. Ventrillard, C. Abd-Alrahman, D. Romanini, « Frequency Comb Based Spectrometer for in Situ and Real Time Measurements of IO, BrO, NO₂, and H₂CO at pptv and ppqv Levels ». *Environmental Science & Technology*, 46(19), 10704–10. doi : [10.1021/es301785h](https://doi.org/10.1021/es301785h) (2012).

10. G. Méjean, R. Grilli, C. Abd-Alrahman, I. Ventrillard, S. Kassi, D. Romanini, « A transportable spectrometer for in situ and local measurements of iodine monoxide at mixing ratios in the 10⁻¹⁴ range ». *Applied Physics Letters*, 100(25), 251110. doi : [10.1063/1.4726190](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4726190) (2012).

9. R. Grilli, G. Méjean, C. Abd-Alrahman, I. Ventrillard, S. Kassi, D. Romanini, « Cavity-enhanced multiplexed comb spectroscopy down to the photon shot noise ». *Physical Review A*, 85(5), 1-5 doi : [10.1103/PhysRevA.85.051804](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevA.85.051804) (2012).

8. R. Grilli, G. Méjean, S. Kassi, I. Ventrillard, C. Abd-Alrahman, E. Fasci, D. Romanini, « Trace measurement of BrO at the ppt level by a transportable mode-locked frequency-doubled cavity-enhanced spectrometer », *Applied Physics B*, doi : [10.1021/la9047825](https://doi.org/10.1021/la9047825) (2010).

7. P. Di Profio, R. Germani, L. Goracci, R. Grilli, M. Tiecco, G. Savelli, « Interaction between DNA and Cationic Amphiphiles : A Multi-Technique Study », *Langmuir*, 26 (11), 7885–7892. doi : [10.1021/la9047825](https://doi.org/10.1021/la9047825) (2010).

6. R. Grilli, L. Ciaffoni and A.J. Orr-Ewing, « Phase-shift cavity ring-down spectroscopy using mid-IR light from a difference frequency generation PPLN waveguide », *Optics Letters*, 35, 1383-1385. doi : [10.1364/OL.35.001383](https://doi.org/10.1364/OL.35.001383) (2010).

5. R. Grilli, L. Ciaffoni, G. Hancock, R. Peverall, G.A.D. Ritchie and A.J. Orr-Ewing, « Mid-IR ethane detection using difference frequency generation in a quasi-phase matched LiNbO₃ waveguide », *Applied Optics*, 48, 5696-5703. doi : [10.1364/AO.48.005696](https://doi.org/10.1364/AO.48.005696) (2009).

4. L. Ciaffoni, R. Grilli, G. Hancock, A.J. Orr-Ewing, R. Peverall and G.A.D. Ritchie, « 3.5 μ m high-resolution gas sensing employing a LiNbO₃ QPM-DFG waveguide module », *Applied Physics B*, 94, 517-525. doi : [10.1007/s00340-008-3291-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00340-008-3291-0) (2009).

3. M. Pradhan, M.S.I. Aziz, R. Grilli, A.J. Orr-Ewing, « Automated system for monitoring trace C₂H₂ in ambient air by cavity ring-down spectroscopy combined with sample pre-concentration », *Environmental Science & Technology*, 42, 7354 - 7359. doi: [10.1021/es801378r](https://doi.org/10.1021/es801378r) (2008).

2. M. Pradhan, R.E. Lindley, R. Grilli, I.R. White, D. Martin, A.J. Orr-Ewing, « Trace detection of C₂H₂ in ambient air using continuous wave cavity ring-down spectroscopy combined with sample pre-concentration », *Applied Physics B*, 90, 1-9. doi : [10.1007/s00396-006-1519-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00396-006-1519-2) (2006).

1. S. Gold, J. Eastoe, R. Grilli, D. C. Steytler, « Branched trichain sulfosuccinates as novel water in CO₂ dispersants », *Colloid and Polymer Science*, 284, 1333–1337. doi :[10.1007/s00396-006-1519-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00396-006-1519-2) (2006).

OTHER PUBLICATIONS

M. Schmid, F. Bärenbold, B. Boehrer, F. Darchambeau, R. Grilli, J. Triest, W. Von Tümpling, « Intercalibration Campaign Measurements in Lake Kivu for Gas Concentration. Report prepared for the Lake Kivu Monitoring Programme (LKMP) of the Energy Development Corporation Limited (EDCL), Kigali, Rwanda ». [online] [Available here](#) (2019).

Grilli R., G. Méjean, M. Legrand, S. Preunkert, D. Romanini, « First investigations of IO, BrO, and NO₂ summer atmospheric levels at a coastal East Antarctic site using mode-locked cavity enhanced absorption spectroscopy ». *Mineralogical Magazine*, 77(5) 1217 (2013).

Grilli R., D. Mellon, J. Kim, M.S.I. Aziz, D. Hamilton, A.J. Orr-Ewing, « Applications of cw Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy to the Study of Trace Atmospheric Constituents ». *Lasers, Sources and Related Photonic Devices*, OSA Technical Digest Series (CD), 1–3 (2010).

CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE PRINT AND AUDIO-VISUAL MEDIAS

[2024] News IRD: « Launch of the French-Vietnamese oceanographic campaign “PLUME” »; <https://www.ige-grenoble.fr/Lancement-de-la-campagne-oceanographique-franco-vietnamienne-PLUME>

[2024] News CNRS: R. Grilli, J. Néméry, « Methane in aquatic environments: a new high-resolution in situ measurement tool ». On IGE website.

[2021] Atelier SMA2M White Paper : « Systèmes de Mesures Autonomes pour l’observation du Milieu Marin ».

[2020] Participation to the Pint of Science « L’innovation pour étudier l’évolution de notre planète », Kiltin’ Pub (Grenoble).

[2020] Intervention in the radio podcast « The sound of Ice, quand le réchauffement climatique donne des frissons ».

[2020] Nouvelles CNRS, J. Chappellaz : « Des pulses de CO₂ dans l’atmosphère du passé ».

[2019 - ...] Mentor of "The Sound of the Ice" Art & Science show which uses the arts to underline the importance of protecting and conserving our planet and its climate. Since 2019 we performed several shows in collaboration with the ICE MEMORY project and the Névé association.

[2019] CAGE (Centre for Arctic Gas Hydrate, Environment and Climate) News Letter: J. Green, « Sophisticated new technology successful in measuring underwater methane distribution in unprecedented detail ».

[2019] CEA News Letter : « Traque européenne du méthane en mer Noire ».

[2019] ENVRIPlus Project Press Released : « Hunting of methane transfer from the seafloor to the atmosphere in the Black Sea by combining european Research Infrastructures ».

[2018] IGE News Letter: R. Grilli, « SUBOCEAN : The first attempt for continuous methane profile of the meromictic Lake Kivu in Rwanda ».

[2016] CAGE (Centre for Arctic Gas Hydrate, Environment and Climate) News Letter: M. Sojtarić, « Arctic Ocean preparations in the hunt for the oldest ice in Antarctica ».

[2016] Innovation Letter CNRS: J. Chappellaz, J. Triest, R. Grilli, « Subglacior : un transfert technologique réussi pour l’analyse haute résolution de gaz dissous ».

[2012] Inspect Journal, D. McCoy and M. Arrigoni, G. Méjean, R. Grilli, S. Kassi, D. Romanini .« Femtosecond laser enables ultrasensitive atmospheric sampling monitoring at a very challenging location ».

[2012] Laser Focus World, « SPECTROSCOPY : Femtosecond laser measures atmospheric-radical traces in Antarctica ».

[2012] Coherent Inc. News Letter, « A Chameleon makes it all the way (and works) down to Antarctica ».

[2012] Coherent Inc. White Paper, « One-Box Ultrafast Lasers : Superior Performance and Reliability ».

SCIENTIFIC EXPEDITIONS

[June 2024] Field campaign in Vietnam

[June 2023] Field campaign at the Lemman Lake (Switzerland)

[June 2022] Oceanographic campaign at the Japanese Sea (Japan)

[Sept 2021] Oceanographic campaign at the Black Sea (Romania)

[Feb 2021] Atmospheric campaign at Chamonix (France)

[July 2019] Atmospheric campaign at the Station Biologique de Roscoff (France)

[June 2019] Field campaign at the Tourbière du Luitel (France)

[May 2019] Field campaign at the Pavan Lake (France)

[May 2019] Field campaign at the Aiguebelette Lake (France)

[April 2019] Oceanographic campaign at the Black Sea (Romania)

[March 2018] Field campaign at Lake Kivu in Rwanda

[Nov 2016 – Feb 2017] Ice core campaign at Concordia Station in Antarctica

[Oct 2015] Oceanographic campaign in Svalbard (Arctic)

[July 2014] Oceanographic campaign at Toulon (France)

[Nov 2011 – Feb 2012] Atmospheric campaign at Dumont D'Urville Station in Antarctica

[June 2011] Test field campaign at the Station Biologique de Roscoff (France)

[Jan 2011] Test field campaign at the Centre d'Océanologie de Marseille (France)

1.4 Outline of my HDR thesis

I divided the HDR manuscript in four main parts: Chapter 2 will be focused on the absorption spectroscopy techniques. I will discuss the use of optical techniques with a variety of light sources at different wavelength regions for tackling different applications. Although on paper many options seems to be possible, we will see that for a specific application, we would have a certain number of constraints that would point toward a specific development. In the following three chapters, I will discuss

the research I carried out in dissolved gas measurements (Chapter 3), atmospheric chemistry (Chapter 4) and ice core science (Chapter 5). At the end of each chapter I will develop conclusions and future perspectives.

2. Absorption spectroscopy techniques

Contents

2.1	The basics of molecular absorption spectroscopy	17
2.2	Direct absorption, multipass cells, or optical cavities? . . .	18
2.3	Different sources, different wavelength regions, different techniques	22

This chapter aims to give an overview of the optical techniques I have used over the past decade, their advantages, disadvantages, and range of applications. The aim is not to give all the required background to understand the fundamentals of absorption spectroscopy, but rather to provide the information on how to use those fundamental knowledge to identify the best technique for a specific application. Up today, many different optical techniques have been developed. Technology is moving forward fast, providing a large variety of always more performing light sources, detection systems, and optical and electro-optical components.

2.1 The basics of molecular absorption spectroscopy

Molecules possess discrete energy levels associated with their electronic, vibrational, and rotational states, and are distributed between those energy states following the Boltzmann distribution. Molecular absorption transitions occur when molecules absorb photons to go from a lower energy state to a higher excited energy state. A photon is therefore absorbed by the molecule when its energy matches the difference in energy between the two states. The photon energy is proportional to the frequency of the transition and inversely proportional to its wavelength. High-energy electronic transitions occur in the ultraviolet (UV) and visible regions: these involve the excitation of an electron from one electronic energy level to a higher one. Vibrational and ro-vibrational transitions occur within a given electronic state and involve changes in the vibrational and rotational energy levels of the molecule. Those transitions are observed in the infrared (IR) region. While pure rotational transitions are lower in energy and occur in the far-infrared and microwave regions. For a molecular transition to be allowed, certain selection rules must be satisfied. These rules are based on quantum mechanical principles and dictate the probability

of a transition to take place. The intensity of a molecular absorption transition is defined by the absorption cross-section (σ) that reflects the probability that the molecule may absorb a photon at a specific energy. Although absorption transitions occur at a specific frequency, those are not infinitely narrow. The absorption lines have a specific shape with width contributions due to the natural line broadening, doppler broadening, and collisional (pressure) broadening. Without getting too much in detail here: natural line broadening gives a Lorentzian contribution to the line shape and is related to the Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle which relates to the fact that the more the excited state is unstable and therefore short in time, the more difficult is to know its energy precisely, which makes the transition line broader. Here collisions with other molecules also play a role in shortening the lifetime of the excited state making molecules get rid of the energy by quenching. The Doppler broadening effect gives a Gaussian contribution and is related to the fact that molecules may move forward or away from the detection, making the frequency of the transition slightly shifted in time. This is the same principle of a moving ambulance making the sound lower or higher in frequency depending on the movement with respect to the observer. The combination of a Lorentzian and a Gaussian shape gives a Voigt profile, which is commonly used in spectroscopy to fit absorption lines. Other effects may also be considered in specific conditions (particularly at low pressure), where the Dicke narrowing effect occurs and should be considered for a better fit of the absorption line. This is called the Rautian profile. More sophisticated line profiles could also be required for high-precision spectroscopy considering for instance the speed-dependent collisional broadening [Tran *et al.* 2013].

2.2 Direct absorption, multipass cells, or optical cavities?

If we send a coherent or incoherent light at a certain frequency (ν) through a cell with an absorbing medium, then the decrease in intensity of the light is defined by the Beer-Lambert law (Figure 2.1a):

$$I_\nu = I_{0,\nu} e^{-\alpha_\nu L} \quad (2.1)$$

$$\alpha_\nu = \sigma_\nu [X] \quad (2.2)$$

where I and I_0 are the intensities of the incoming and exiting light, α is the absorption coefficient, corresponding to the attenuation of the light per cm of the optical path, L is the optical path length, $[X]$ the concentration of the absorber in molecules cm^{-3} and σ , in this case, is the wavelength-dependent absorption coefficient in $\text{cm}^2 \text{molecules}^{-1}$. We can also find in literature integrated absorption cross sections which are integrated over the absorption line and are expressed in $\text{cm}^2 \text{molecules}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$. For trace gas detection applications, the low concentration of the absorption specie requires to work (when possible) at spectral regions where the absorption cross-section is strong and use an optical technique which provide an

adequate optical path length. In certain cases direct absorption (which consists of making a single or a double pass through a measurement cell) may be sufficient, we will see just below the example for the detection of atmospheric $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ and $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ 2.2. An easy way to further increase the sensitivity is by using multipass cells (Figure 2.1b). Here, the light is making several passages inside the cell by reflecting on high reflectivity mirrors (usually with a reflectivity $> 99\%$) placed at both sides of the cell. Holes on the mirrors allow the beam to enter and exit the cell without power losses and a particular pattern is designed at the mirror surfaces to maximize the number of passages while making the spots as far as possible from each other (Figure 2.1d). This is important for avoiding interferences of the electromagnetic fields between neighbor spots which cause optical fringes on the transmitted signal and therefore a degradation of the sensitivity of the measurement. An alternative way for making a beam folding cell has recently been developed by the research group at EMPA in Switzerland. It consists of a segmented circular MPC with a diameter of 8 cm that allows up to 15 (4) m of optical path length and a relatively low volume of about 140 (30) cm^3 . The authors also proposed to add an aperture mask inside the cell for suppressing optical fringes by truncating the divergent radiation at each reflection, at the price of a setup more difficult to optimize and align [Graf *et al.* 2018].

For further enhancing the optical path length, resonant cavities may be used (Figure 2.1c). Here, a comprehensive introduction chapter on cavity-based optical techniques goes through most of them and provides a generous list of literature works [Romanini *et al.* 2014]. In this case, the light beam is aligned on the central axes of the resonator, and the photons are trapped inside the cavity for a time that is directly related to the mirror reflectivity, R . The effective path length is enhanced by a factor $\sim 1/(1-R)$: with a 1-m long cell and mirror reflectivity of 99.99 %, one can obtain optical path lengths of 10 Km. The so-called ring-down time (τ), which is the traveling time of the photons inside the resonator, for a linear two-mirror cavity is expressed as follows:

$$\tau = \frac{L}{c(1-R)} \quad (2.3)$$

Where L is the cavity length, c is the speed of light and R is the reflectivity of the mirrors. When a coherent beam is coupled with an optical cavity, every time the length of the cell is an integer multiple of half of the wavelength of the laser, a standing wave is formed inside the resonator. This leads to a frequency discretization of the spectrum, with cavity modes spaced by a free-spectral range (FSR) of the resonator, that can be used as a frequency ruler.

$$FSR = \frac{c}{2L} \quad (2.4)$$

Different techniques can be found within the Cavity-Enhanced Absorption Spectroscopy (CEAS) methods: the Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy (CRDS), which measures the time it takes the photons to escape from the resonator. For an empty cavity, this only relates to the mirror's losses, while the ring-down time is further decreased in the presence of absorption by the medium inside the cell. One of the main

a) Direct absorption

b) Multipass cells

d)

e)

c) Optical cavities

Figure 2.1: (a) A schematic of direct absorption spectroscopy. A light of intensity I passes through a cell with an absorbing medium. Its intensity is decreased to I_0 following the Beer-Lambert law (equation 2.1); the light path can be enhanced to tens up to hundreds of meters using multipass cells (b) or up to kilometers using optical cavities (c). (d) an example of the spot distribution on a Herriot cell; (e) a drawing of the circular MPC developed at EMPA.

advantages of this technique is that it is immune to the amplitude noise of the laser, since the ring-down time is not dependent on the intensity at the beginning of the exponential decay. This technique is used by the commercial Picarro's instruments. A similar technique but which is usually less sensitive than the standard CRDS is the phase-shift CRDS, which uses a radiation that is modulated in amplitude, and the effective optical path is calculated by measuring the phase-shift caused by the long path.

One of the main drawbacks of the cavity-based technique is the fact that the more we increase the reflectivity of the mirrors, the more is difficult to inject light inside the resonator. With reflectivity of 99.99% less than 0.01% of light can enter

the cavity, plus there is a frequency filtering: the higher the reflectivity, the higher the cavity finesse, F , the narrower is the cavity resonance, $\Delta\nu$.

$$F = \frac{\pi\sqrt{R}}{1-R} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\Delta\nu = \frac{FSR}{F} \quad (2.6)$$

A resonant width $\Delta\nu$ is typically a few kHz while a distributed feedback (DFB) laser has a typical bandwidth of the emission of a few MHz. The Optical Feedback - Cavity Enhanced Absorption Spectroscopy (OF-CEAS) [Morville *et al.* 2005, Morville *et al.* 2014] discovered at LIPhy in Grenoble overcomes this problem. It uses a three-mirror V-shaped cavity for sending the photons that are in resonant with the cavity back to the laser. This forces the laser to emit photons at the frequency of the resonator, reducing the bandwidth and the phase noise of the laser and leading to a more efficient injection into the cavity. This technique is used by AP2E commercial sensors and will be used for application in aquatic environments in Chapter 3. A powerful technique that has been developed by the group at LIPhy consists of coupling together OF-CEAS and CRDS and it is called VCOF-CRDS for V-shaped Cavity Optical Feedback - Cavity Ring Down Spectroscopy. The idea is to generate an ultra-narrow laser source by making optical feedback on an ultra-stable V-shaped three-mirror cavity. Afterward, a single side-band with suppression of the carrier is made for tuning this laser source in frequency and then injected it into a CRDS cavity for molecular detection [Stoltmann *et al.* 2017]. There are other variants of the CEAS technique, such as off-axis CEAS, which misaligns the laser beam to the resonator axes in propose to excite higher-order modes. Those are spatial modes that can be excited and because the beam is no longer traveling at the central axes of the cavity, those high-order modes resonate at different frequencies. Increasing the number of modes allows one to have a continuum transmission at the price of lower intensity at the cavity output. OA-CEAS often uses either amplitude or wavelength modulation techniques to decrease the detection bandwidth and improve the signal-to-noise ratio of the transmitted signal. Similarly, we can inject incoherent light (from a lamp or a LED) for which the resonator will increase the optical path length but there will be no standing wave forming inside the resonator and no spatial mode excitation. While the OA-CEAS uses narrow lasers that are swept in frequency, the incoherent broadband technique (IBB-CEAS) allows broad spectra to be acquired in a single acquisition and requires multiplexing detection. This technique is further described in Chapter 4. Broadband spectra can also be obtained with coherent radiation, using frequency combs (femtosecond lasers). Depending on the way of looking the comb of the laser with the one of the resonator, different techniques can be found. The one developed in Grenoble is called Mode-Locked CEAS (ML-CEAS) and consists of making a fast scan near the resonance making the laser comb tooth getting in resonance with the cavity at the same speed even if not necessarily exactly at the same time. This allowed a

more robust setup for field deployment than a tight-locking approach, while pushing the detection to the quantum-noise limit [Grilli *et al.* 2012a]. The group of A. Foltynowicz at Umeå University in Sweden developed a similar setup but using a Fourier transform spectrometer and obtaining a detection at the shot-noise limit as well [Foltynowicz *et al.* 2011]. Dual-comb spectroscopy may also be used with optical cavities. It consists of using two frequency comb sources with a slightly different repetition rate and by mixing the two laser beams in a single photo-detector, an interferogram in the radio-frequency domain can be obtained. This detection scheme is called multi-heterodyne, and it is powerful but requires two frequency comb sources which are relatively bulky and expensive. A phase locking of the two combs or an adaptive system for taking into account that the two combs are moving one with respect to the other is needed [Bernhardt *et al.* 2010, Ideguchi *et al.* 2014].

2.3 Different sources, different wavelength regions, different techniques

In trace gas detection, the selection of light sources is crucial as it significantly impacts the sensitivity and selectivity of the measurement techniques. Depending on the wavelength region and the absorption techniques employed, coherent or incoherent light sources can be used. Coherent light sources produce light that is highly monochromatic and phase-coherent, making them ideal for high-resolution spectroscopy. These sources are particularly useful in narrow wavelength regions where precision is crucial. Lasers such as diode lasers, Quantum Cascade Lasers (QCLs), and Interband Cascade Lasers (ICLs) provide high intensity and narrow line widths. QCLs, for instance, are highly effective in the mid-infrared region (3-20 μm), an interesting region to probe ro-vibrational transitions of molecules. ICLs are also for the mid-IR, room temperature ICLs operate from 3 to 5.7 μm , while cooled ones may span up to 11 μm . The advantage of ICLs with respect to QCLs is the lower consumption, similar to standard telecom DFB diode lasers. For broadband spectrum coherent laser sources, frequency comb lasers are used. Titanium-Sapphire (Ti:Sa) Lasers are probably the most common sources of frequency combs in the visible and near-infrared regions. They typically operate around 675 to 1100 nm. Fiber Lasers, like Erbium-doped fiber lasers, can produce frequency combs in the NIR region, around 1.55 μm , which is a standard telecommunications wavelength. Due to the high peak intensity, non-linear effects such as second harmonic generation, optical parametric oscillators, etc. are efficient, and allow broadening the wavelength span moving either to the UV or to the mid- and far-IR region. A supercontinuum emission can also be produced by passing intense ultrafast laser pulses through a photonic crystal fiber (which is a nonlinear medium, as well). The high peak power of these pulses induces a range of nonlinear optical processes, including self-phase modulation, four-wave mixing, and Raman scattering, which collectively broaden the spectrum to generate the supercontinuum. Incoherent light sources, like LED, lamps or Laser Driven Light Sources (LDLS), emit light over a broad range of wave-

2.3. Different sources, different wavelength regions, different techniques

Figure 2.2: Simulation for 400 ppm of $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ and $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ at the corresponding natural abundance in the mid-IR region on one side, and the one for 10 ppm of $^{12}\text{CH}_4$ and the corresponding $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ both at 10 mbar pressure. This figure shows how the strength of the absorption transition would affect the choice of the optical technique to be used. Dashed red lines represent the absorption corresponding to the attenuation of the light by 1% for different optical path lengths.

lengths but do not maintain phase coherence. They can be used with optical cavities as described in the previous section but they do not form a standing wave inside the resonator as coherent sources. They are also commonly used for Long-Path - Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (LP-DOAS).

Therefore, depending on what we want to detect, single or multiple species, in which range of concentrations, with what sensitivity, at what acquisition rate, for which type of applications and deployment, then one can select a specific technique with an adapted light source at a specific wavelength region. In Figure 2.2 is reported a simulation of spectra for isotopic measurement of CO_2 and CH_4 in the mid-IR region. Due to the stronger abundance of CO_2 in the atmosphere, the absorption of the $^{13}\text{CO}_2$ lines reaches a few percent in intensity with only 1 m of optical path length, while the $^{13}\text{CH}_4$ detection at atmospheric levels would require the use of optical cavities. Often, spectral interference with other molecules should also be considered, for instance, there are regions where water vapor is strongly absorbed, and light transmission would become too poor for long path lengths. In this case, so-called transparency windows should be preferred. For high-precision isotopic measurements, well-isolated absorption lines should be selected, to avoid any possible artifact due to the change in concentration of the interfering species.

Often, scientists discover a novel technique, and after testing what it is capable of, would start to think of possible applications. In my way of working, I rather start from the problem and need, and I will think of how I could develop an instrument that would respect the specific constraints in terms of sensitivity, accuracy, concentration range, type and amount of sample, type of experiment (laboratory, on-site, *in situ*), etc.

Applications to dissolved gas measurements

Contents

3.1	Introduction	25
3.2	<i>In situ</i> dissolved gases measurements: CH₄, δ¹³CH₄ and C₂H₆	27
3.2.1	The first applications of the SubOcean instrument for high-resolution mapping of dissolved methane	29
3.2.2	More recent field campaigns with the SubOcean probe and the technology transfer	33
3.3	<i>In situ</i> water isotope measurements: δD, δ¹⁸O and δ¹⁷O of H₂O	35
3.3.1	Introduction and scientific motivation	35
3.3.2	The Subsea water isotope sensor	36
3.3.3	Field applications	40
3.4	Conclusion and perspectives	41

3.1 Introduction

It is today established that the rapid increase in atmospheric concentrations of carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄) and nitrous oxide (N₂O) since pre-industrial times is due to human activities. The accumulation of these greenhouse gases (GHGs) in the atmosphere is determined by the balance between natural and anthropogenic emissions and adsorptions, and the physico-biogeochemical dynamics of sources and sinks in lands and oceans. The contributions of aquatic sources such as continental waters (lakes, rivers and wetlands) and oceans play a crucial role in the carbon cycle. Today, GHG emission flows are poorly documented and quantified, and their dynamics and forcing are poorly understood. For example, methane fluxes from wetlands and aquatic reservoirs on a global scale have recently increased, and represent a major uncertainty as well as the role of these ecosystems in climate regulation [Saunois *et al.* 2019]. Better characterizing the sequestration, transformation, transport, and emission of GHGs by terrestrial aquatic systems is

therefore a crucial challenge if we want to achieve carbon neutrality and limit global warming.

Today, dissolved gas measurements are carried out using either equipment to collect water samples followed by laboratory analysis, or by available *in situ* dissolved gas sensors, characterized by slow response time and/or uncertain reliability (this is the case for the HydroC from 4H-Jena and the METS and LMS sensor from Franatech). Pro-Oceanus has recently made efforts to improve miniaturization and response speed, but like its competitors, it does not offer a multi-species sensor, its response time remains slow (t_{90} of ~ 20 min) for spatial monitoring of dissolved gas, and its reliability is uncertain.

Membrane Inlet Mass Spectrometers (MIMS) are now commercialized, and their usefulness for high-resolution mapping has been proven by several studies.[Chua *et al.* 2016, Mächler *et al.* 2012, Tortell 2005] However, they are still cumbersome, heavy, and energy-consuming for some AUVs, gliders, drones, or instrumented buoys, as well as for long-term observations, and they lack in selectivity due to their limitation in achieving high mass resolution with compact systems, which would also limit the possibility to perform isotopic measurements. Orbitrap is an emerging and promising mass spectrometry technique, but it is less suitable for measuring dissolved gases because they are not easily ionized[Makarov 2000].

In situ Raman spectroscopy has also been used to analyze the chemical composition of water and detect dissolved gases. This technology is compact and well-suited for field applications, but its lack of sensitivity makes it suitable only for measurements close to the source [Zhang *et al.* 2017].

Attempts to use the ability of supramolecular cryptophane-A to trap methane molecules have been presented in the literature, without any follow-up towards a marketable system [Boulart *et al.* 2008, Dullo *et al.* 2015]. Although they have the prerequisites for compact, low-power dissolved gas sensors, their application is so far limited to measuring the molecular concentration of CH_4 , and their selectivity is highly dependent on the selected supramolecular compound. Finally, for concentration measurement, a range of compact, low-cost gas sensors is available today (SenseAir, Atlas-Scientific, Vaisala, Figaro, Cubic, Olythe, etc.). However, it should be noted that these sensors are designed for atmospheric measurements, and would require some readaptation and validation work before being used for dissolved gas measurements. In addition, these sensors may be dependent on the type of environment (humidity, temperature, oxygen content) and lack selectivity (interference caused by the presence of other molecular species or by a change in ambient light).

This motivated me to work on fast-response dissolved gas sensors. The development started in 2014, and since then we had three versions of the prototype, each time we made the sensor more compact and better designed, and we moved from only concentration measurements to also *in situ* isotopic ratio measurements. In the following section, I will explain the concept of the instrument, present its performance, and detail the various applications we have carried out so far.

Manufacturer - Sensor name	Technology	Measuring in water	Multi-species	Dimensions Weight	Power consumption	Response time	Sensitivity	Selectivity	Reliability
4H-Jena - Contros - HydroC	MILS	●	●	●	●	●	●	○(NC)	●
Franatech -METS	détecteur à semi-conducteur SnO2	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Franatech - LMS	MILS	●	●	●	●	●	●	○(NC)	○(NC)
Pro-Oceanus - Solu Blue ou mini CH4	Pas mentionné	●	●	●	●	●	●	○(NC)	●
Winsen - ZP04 Figaro - TGS	détecteur à semi-conducteur	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Cubic - SJH-5	NDIR	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Atlans-Scientific - EZO-CO2	NDIR	●	●	●	●	●	●	○(NC)	○(NC)
Vaisala - GMP252	NDIR	●	●	●	●	●	●	○(NC)	●
Olythe - OCIEngine PRO	NDIR	●	●	●	●	●	●	○(NC)	○(NC)
Spectroscopie Raman	Multi-RIPs	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
Spyglass S200	MIMS	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●
A2 Photonic Sensors - SubOcean	MILS	●	●	●	●	●	●	●	●

Figure 3.1: Non-exhaustive comparison of existing sensors for dissolved gas measurement, or sensors for atmospheric measurement that could possibly be adapted for measurement in water (NC: unknown)

3.2 *In situ* dissolved gases measurements: CH_4 , $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ and C_2H_6

Most of the instruments working with a semipermeable membrane for extracting dissolved gas from a liquid rely on the equilibration of the gas across the membrane. The liquid circulates on one side of the membrane, and the driving force that causes the gas to adsorb, permeate, and desorb the membrane is its partial pressure difference between the water solution and the air on the other side of the membrane. This process is generally slow, on the order of a few tens of minutes and it is further slower when the gas has to re-dissolve in the liquid, which occurs in case of a decrease of dissolved gas concentration in the liquid phase.

In our case, we decided to force the permeation through the membrane by maintaining the dry side of the membrane at low pressure, while continuously flushing it with dry “zero air” gas. The pressure at the membrane’s dry side controls the total flow of dry and wet air through the membrane and can be used to adjust

Figure 3.2: **Top:** Schematic principle of the Sub-Ocean instrument. The water circulation pump ensures a flow of about 800 ml min^{-1} of water at the membrane that is mounted in a membrane block (MB). The dry side of the membrane is continuously flushed with a small (1 to 6 sccm) dry gas flow supplied by the gas tank, a pressure reducer, P_{red} and a mass flow meter, MFC_{CG} . The mixture (carrier gas plus extracted gas) is then sent to the optical spectrometer. The total flow is measured by a second mass flow controller, MFC_{TF} . The pressure in the measurement cell of the spectrometer is regulated at 30 mbar using a pressure meter, an electro-valve (EV) and a vacuum pump (VP). A dryer made of silica gel is used to reduce the water vapour reaching the vacuum pump. **Bottom:** a picture of the instrument.

the amount of water vapor permeating the membrane. Gas permeation through a membrane depends on the solubility in the membrane itself, followed by diffusion (migration of molecules through the membrane lattice) and finally evaporation out of the membrane [Zhang & Cloud 2006]. Other than the partial pressure difference across the membrane, the membrane thickness or pore size, water flow at the membrane, and ambient temperature affect the permeation: lower thickness (higher pore size), larger flow, and higher temperature lead to higher permeability and therefore faster response time. With respect to the membrane properties, higher temperature increases the free volume as well as the mobility of the polymer chain, leading to higher diffusivity of gases through the membrane. With respect to any given gas, higher temperature means higher mobility, diffusivity, and permeability. Water flow needs to be controlled and water temperature measured for accurately

retrieving the dissolved gas concentration. Biofouling, salinity, hydrostatic pressure, and pH of the water may also affect the efficiency of the permeability. The optical technique used in this development is the Optical Feedback - Cavity Enhanced Absorption Spectroscopy (OF-CEAS, see Chapter 2). During a frequency scan, the laser emission is locked on the successive narrow cavity resonances which improves the laser/cavity coupling and therefore the signal intensity at the output of the resonator. This makes the OF-CEAS technique highly sensitive on the absorption axes, with a regular rule on the frequency axes provided by the optical resonator [Morville *et al.* 2005, Morville *et al.* 2014].

The schematic and a picture of the SubOcean instrument, also known as a Membrane Inlet Laser Spectrometer (MILS) is reported in Figure 3.2. More information about the instrument are available in [Grilli *et al.* 2018].

In Table 3.1 are reported the performance of the SubOcean instrument, including the range of concentrations that can be measured, the precisions for both concentrations and isotopic measurements and the response time of the instrument. The casing of the instrument have been realized in titanium for larger deployment depths (3,000 m below sea level) and a lighter POM casing for shallow deployment (up to 30 m depth). In Table 3.2 the physical specifications are reported, including dimensions, weight, power consumption and autonomy of the instrument. The operator can communicate with the instrument by WiFi connection, practical during the preparation of the instrument on the boats or platforms, and by a Single-pair High-speed Digital Subscriber Line (SHDLS) protocol while in water. The latter, similar to an ADSL protocol, allow a relatively fast communication (we obtained 768 kbit/s over a 3,000 m long electromechanical cable) using a two-wires cable.

The instrument has been deployed at different locations: in the Arctic [Jansson *et al.* 2019], at Lake Kivu in Rwanda [Grilli *et al.* 2020, Bärenbold *et al.* 2020], in the Black Sea [Grilli *et al.* 2021], at Lake Aiguebelette [Grilli *et al.* 2023], in the Japan Sea in 2022, in Norway, Cap Coarse, Lake Lemman and in Greenland in 2023 and in Vietnam in 2024. Below, I reported a summary of the main achievements from some of those field campaigns.

3.2.1 The first applications of the SubOcean instrument for high-resolution mapping of dissolved methane

The Arctic campaign took place near the Svalbards in October 2015, and was a first "real" deployment after a test campaign in the Mediterranean Sea in July 2014. The campaign was organized by our colleague from CAGE (Centre for Arctic Gas Hydrate, Environment and Climate) at the University of Tromsø (UiT) in Norway and was on board of the R/V Helmer Hanssen. The SubOcean instrument was deployed over a region with about 400m of water depth where the UiT already identified the presence of flares (bubble streams identified by an acoustic echo-sounder). In this area at the seabed, the methane hydrates are outside the stability zone (physical conditions of 40 bar of hydrostatic pressure, 4°C of water temperature and 35 psu of salinity) which motivates the selection of the region of study. Prior to the

Table 3.1: Summary of the performance of the SubOcean instrument

Performance specifications		
	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₆
Measurement range	0 - 10,000 ppm (0 - 14 μ M)	0 - 400 ppm (0 - 0.7 μ M)
Range for δ^{13} C ratio	2 - 1,000 ppm	
Concentration Accuracy	\pm 5% (of CH ₄)	\pm 5% (of C ₂ H ₆), \pm 0.05‰ (of CH ₄)
δ^{13} C ratio Accuracy	2‰ - 6‰	
limit of detection (LOD)	0.03 ppm (0.05 nM)	1 ppb (2 pM)
Equilibration rate (t ₉₀)	typ. 30 s (min 15s - max 3 min)	
Depth Rating	3,000 m with titanium casing, 30m with POM casing	
Water temperature range	-1.8°C to 35°C	

Table 3.2: Summary of the physical specification of the SubOcean instrument

Physical specifications	
Dimensions	Instrument: 100 cm x ϕ 19 cm Battery: 28.5 cm x ϕ 19 cm
Housing Material	Titanium or POM
Weight	Titanium version: 52 kg + battery : 20 kg POM version: 20 kg + battery : 8.7 kg
Power consumption	40 W
Battery type	Li-Ion 24 VDC
Battery life	12 h
Output	WiFi or Ethernet/SHDSL

campaign, the spatial variability of the dissolved CH₄ in the water column was not well constraint and previous works were tempted to estimate methane fluxes from the seabed using discrete low-resolution data, assuming that the concentration of dissolved CH₄ was relatively homogeneous on the lateral axes [Graves *et al.* 2015]. Thanks to the fast response of the SubOcean sensor, in three days of survey we could make verticals and horizontal profiles over an area of 18 km², revealing for the first time the fast variability and the strong in-homogeneity of dissolved CH₄ in

the water.

Figure 3.3: **(a)** Towed MILS data from the SubOcean instrument overlying echosounder data. The black line shows the CH_4 concentration at about 15m from the seafloor. The blue line indicates the depth of the probe. The echogram, displaying target strength values (color bar shows intensity -dB) from the 38 kHz channel of the EK60, is shown in the background; **(b)** temperature and salinity data together with the depth of the towed instruments. The dashed-line box highlights the area of intense mixing; In **(c)**, the red line shows again the dissolved CH_4 measured by the MILS. The grey area indicates the range of CH_4 concentrations from 2-D model simulations. The black line depicts the output of the model simulation with the best match with the measured concentrations.

We deployed our sensor together with a slow-response commercial instrument based on the equilibration technique. By convoluting our fast response signal with an exponential function with a time constant of about 40 min we could see a good agreement between the two slow-response observations, proving the reliability of our sensor. The colleagues from UiT further worked on this dataset and used it to optimize a deconvolution routine for extracting the high-frequency information from the slow response sensor data. The model allowed to reconstruct the fast response signal with a correlation coefficient of 0.91 while comparing it with the fast-response data of the SubOcean sensor [Dølven *et al.* 2022].

This first high-resolution data of dissolved CH_4 result was exceptional for us. We proved for the first time that areas with gas flare emissions are characterized by a strong spatial variability of the dissolved gas signal, at the scale of few tens of meters.

Here, the density stratification plays an important role in the vertical distribution of dissolved CH_4 because turbulent energy is required to mix solvents across isopycnals. Vertical mixing seems inhibited even without the presence of strong pycnoclines, and vertical profiles show that dissolved CH_4 is mainly present in the water column at the first 100 m from the seabed, where the vertical distribution of dissolved CH_4 follows an exponential dissolution function. The observed height limit seems therefore a result of rapid bubble dissolution and inefficient vertical mixing, regardless of the existence of pronounced pycnoclines.

Concerning the horizontal variability, water currents play a role in displacing the water mass but the mixing remains weak, leading to the high spatial variability that we discovered. This highlights the importance of high-resolution mapping of dissolved gas, for obtaining a more representative documentation of the presence of dissolved gas in the water column, important for flux estimation as well as for understanding the processes of transport and transformation of the dissolved gas in the water column.

After this first discovery, we continue to work on the miniaturization and the improvement of the SubOcean sensor as well as its deployment in different environments and settings. In 2018, the instrument was deployed at Lake Kivu in Rwanda, where we had to deal with extremely high dissolved CH_4 concentrations. The campaign allowed us to compare our instrument with other on-site and laboratory methods for measuring dissolved gas [Schmid *et al.* 2019, Bärenbold *et al.* 2020]. Our instrument also allowed us to perform precise measurements of the shallower 150m of water column [Grilli *et al.* 2020]. At the black sea in Romania in 2019 [Grilli *et al.* 2021] and 2021, in collaboration with IFREMER and the LSCE. We performed vertical profiles at sites with different water depths, spanning from 50 to 1400m, and a surface study for estimating fluxes at the surface. For the latter, we measured dissolved CH_4 concentration at 5 m water depth using the SubOcean instrument and the atmospheric concentrations with a commercial Picarro instrument on a few Km^2 area at each site. This work allowed us to conclude that, at sites with water depth larger than 150 m CH_4 fluxes toward the atmosphere are small $\sim 1 \text{ mmol m}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ and get five times higher at sites with shallower water depth.

In 2019 we did a field campaign at lake Aiguebelette, near Grenoble in France. The aim for the campaign was to provide concentrations of dissolved CH_4 at the lake surface for validating the measurement from a hyper-spectral camera that was developed by the Institute for Planetary Sciences and Astrophysics (IPAG) of Grenoble. But the 2D surface mapping of CH_4 and $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ was so detailed that we used this dataset for a better understanding of the biogeochemical process at work. In our work [Grilli *et al.* 2023], conducted in collaboration with T. DelsSontro from the University of Waterloo, we highlight the importance of the high-resolution data for a more representative estimation of the dissolved gas in the littoral zone (where the higher variability is observed). And we showed how, the high resolution, allow a more precise and representative identification of the processes at work, with CH_4 oxidation prevailing over epilimnetic production. By looking at the change in the $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ with respect to the CH_4 concentration as a function of the lake area for

Aiguebelette and other previously studied North American lakes, we observed a negative exponential relationship. This relationship is likely explained by the fact that smaller lakes have a larger littoral-to-total area ratio with the littoral zone being the location where a large portion of methane production occurs [Grilli *et al.* 2023].

3.2.2 More recent field campaigns with the SubOcean probe and the technology transfer

Since the beginning of 2018 with the help of the SATT (Technology Transfer Acceleration Unit in Grenoble) a technology transfer of this technology for fast measurement of dissolved gas has been undergoing. The company Contros (which became Kongsberg Maritime first and now 4H-JENA) was the first one to show high interest in this technology but the license agreement has never been signed. In March 2021 the company in Grenoble [A2 Photonic Sensors](#) expressed an interest in this technology. A2 Photonic Sensors specializes in the design and commercialisation of sensors for water, snow and ice applications in small series, mainly for the academic and research sectors.

In July 2022 the licence agreement was signed and the technological transfer toward this company could start. With A2 Photonic Sensors we have now established a pleasant and fruitful cooperation, with the first two commercial instruments which have been recently finalized, and field campaigns that we performed in collaboration.

In the summer of 2022 we performed a campaign in Japan in collaboration with the National Institute of Advanced Industrial Science and Technology (AIST) in Tsukuba. The instrument was installed on the ROV (Remote Operated Vehicle) the Leopard from Saab Seaeye Ltd, and in six days of field campaign, we mapped with high-resolution the dissolved CH₄, δ¹³CH₄ and C₂H₆ near the seabed at different areas. The data valorization is undergoing and led by colleagues from AIST.

In May 2023, the laboratory prototype was used by colleagues from EPFL in a campaign in Norway organized by CAGE (Centre for Arctic Gas Hydrate, Environment and Climate) at the UiT in Tromsø.

In June 2023 the instrument was deployed at Lake Lemman, in Switzerland. A peak of CH₄ was previously observed by the team of Didier Jezequel at CARTEL-INRAE at a depth of about ~12 m at the [LéXPLORE platform](#). The intensity of this peak increases over summer, when the lake is stratified reaching a maximum in July and then it decreases back. The reason of the presence of this methane-enriched layer is so far unknown. We therefore used the SubOcean probe for performing north-to-south 2D transects going from the Rhone delta on the east side of the Lake to the central part. The transects highlight the presence of few hot spots near by the Rhone delta with CH₄ emissions from the sediments, and we could clearly capture the formation of this well-stratified methane-enriched layer at ~12 m depth while moving to the western part of the lake. The campaign was conducted by IGE, CARTEL, EPFL and UNIL, and the data analysis and interpretation are ongoing by a PhD student at UNIL to see if this enriched layer is originated by the transport of the water masses or by *in situ* local production by the microorganisms.

Figure 3.4: Picture of the SubOcean in situ dissolved gas sensor installed on the ROV Leopard.

In July 2023 the company A2 Photonic Sensor took part to the Gombessa 6 mission, organized by Andromede Ocean for digging into the mystery of coralligenous rings that we can found at ~ 100 m of water depth at Cap Corse. The SubOcean probe mapped the area to see if the presence of dissolved methane could not explain the eventual formation of those rings. [A documentary on the Arte channel](#) is currently underway, with a scientific explanation of this mystery!

In June 2024 the SubOcean took part to the PLUME campaign in Vietnam for documenting the spatial variability of dissolved gas in the land-to-sea continuum in Saigon River and Mekong Delta.

3.3 *In situ* water isotope measurements: δD , $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ of H_2O

The instrument was developed during the ANR JCJC "SWIS" (2019-2022) of which I was the PI. The development was carried out with the engineer Camille Blouzon. From February to June 2021, the student Axel Wohleber did a M2 internship on the first validation of the instrument for measuring water isotopes. Axel continued the work of improvement and validation of the sensor within his PhD thesis which started in October 2021 and of which I was the supervisor. Several improvements on the sensor were carried on during his PhD, and the instrument reached an accuracy that allows now the first applications in the field. The instrument was tested in the Black sea in September 2021, then at Lac Lemman in October 2022 and July 2023, and it was deployed through a borehole at Fimbul ice-shelf in Antarctica during the Austral summer 2023-2024. A paper describing the instrument and its performance was led by Axel and submitted to *Limnology and Oceanography : Methods* journal in June 2024.

3.3.1 Introduction and scientific motivation

Since the 1950s, water isotopes have been identified as conservative tracers in seawater similar to salinity [Craig & Gordon 1965]. At the ocean surface, δD and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of water increase during evaporation and decrease during precipitation. Away from the surface, these two signatures represent conservative tracers, allowing the reconstruction of the origin and evolution of water masses. The principal difference between these isotopic signatures and salinity is that isotopic signatures related to precipitations decrease with latitude. Moving toward polar regions, abundances of the precipitations in the heavy isotopes will decrease, reaching $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values as low as -55 (-20) ‰ and δD values around -400 (-50) ‰ in the South (North) polar regions [Frew *et al.* 2000, Lhomme *et al.* 2005]. As a consequence, differently from salinity, following the spatial and temporal variability of the isotopic composition of seawater provides a direct link to the freshwater cycle, that will contribute to discriminate between different water sources, such as those coming from glacier and sea ice melting, sub-glacial outflows and precipitations [Bigg & Rohling 2000, Frew *et al.* 2000, Brown *et al.* 2014] .

Today, the variability of isotopes of water or noble gases in the ocean remains scarcely documented because of the difficulty of making precise mapping of isotopic ratio in water masses. Both measurements are conducted by laboratory analysis of discrete water samples using Niskin bottles or similar sampling systems. This method is time-consuming and limited in spatial and temporal resolution due to its discrete nature. As highlighted in the previous section discussing about dissolved gas variability, a poor resolution may lead to a lack of information and therefore to inexact scientific conclusion. Having a tool for *in situ* high resolution measurements of water isotopes will help discriminating between different water sources in aquatic systems, leading to a large number of information which will be key in the

understanding of processes at work in various water environments.

One of the main applications for this *in situ* sensor for measuring water isotopes is the understanding and quantification of the processes at work in the interaction between the oceans and ice shelves for better projecting future sea level rise. The ice shelf-ocean environment involves numerous processes and interactions that make it difficult to fully understand the mechanisms and identify the links between ocean circulation under the ice shelf and the ice shelf mass balance. The evolution of ice shelf melt will fundamentally depend on their interactions with ocean water masses. For anticipating future ice shelf trends, it is therefore of prime importance to understand how these water masses interact and to identify the dominant processes. Water mass identification usually relies on physical measurements of their temperature and salinity. However, the real environment is more complex, with numerous processes affecting these physical parameters, e.g., through brine formation from sea ice growth, ice shelf basal melting and refreezing, air-sea interactions, tidal currents, surface and sub-glacial runoff, and iceberg melting.

Tides, for example, have been reported as important drivers of ice-shelf basal melting at diurnal and semi-diurnal frequencies [Padman *et al.* 2018], as well as the existence of sub-shelf channels and their role on the ice shelf thinning [Rintoul *et al.* 2016, Gourmelen *et al.* 2017]. Therefore, there is a major interest for obtaining measurements at the process spatial and time scales.

To measure stable water isotopes, different methods exist such as Isotope Ratio Mass Spectroscopy (IRMS) [Walker *et al.* 2016] or absorption spectroscopic methods using optical resonators or multi-pass cells [Walker *et al.* 2016, Dyroff *et al.* 2010]. The determination of the isotopic composition by IRMS method is bulky, expensive and time-consuming (therefore only adapted to laboratory analysis), while optical spectroscopy techniques reach similar performances while being more compact, less expensive and easier to use [Walker *et al.* 2016, Kerstel 2004].

3.3.2 The Subsea water isotope sensor

The optical technique used in this development is the OF-CEAS as in the previous section. Although in this case we can work with high water vapour concentrations, the access to the less abundant isotopologues and the constraint of identifying a narrow region with comparable normalized absorption for the different isotopologues still require the use of optical cavities. To perform high-precision isotopic ratio measurements with the OF-CEAS technique, the absorption lines should have an intensity on the order of 10^{-6} cm^{-1} . This order of intensity allow to use the full dynamic range of the technique and therefore an optimum signal-to-noise ratio on the acquired spectra. At higher absorption levels, the optical feedback at the top of the absorption lines decreases, leading to narrow and weak resonance modes which compromise the precision in the retrieved peak surfaces. According to those criteria, the wavelength region around 1967 nm was selected, allowing simultaneous measurement of H_2^{16}O , H_2^{18}O , H_2^{17}O and HD^{16}O . The absorption lines are sufficiently separated from each other. Regarding other possible interferences, there is

3.3. *In situ* water isotope measurements: δD , $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ of H_2O 37

a CO_2 line at 1967.7 nm, but it is well isolated from the water lines and the inlet system is designed to minimize the permeation of dissolved.

Figure 3.5: (a) Schematic and (b) picture of the Subsea Water Isotopic Sensor (SWIS) instrument. PSV: Proportional Solenoid Valve, MB: Membrane block with reference water, EC: electronic cards, FM: Flowmeter

Water isotope ratio measurements for the ^{18}O and D isotopic ratios require accuracy of 0.05 ‰ and 0.5 ‰, respectively, to resolve the variability expected nearby Antarctic ice shelves [Akhoudas *et al.* 2020]. To validate the possibility of the instrument to obtain these accuracies, we performed a statistical Allan Variance test that tells us the expected precision for a given average time, and from a long-time analysis the potential degradation of the signal due to the rise of instrumental drifts. In our case, the three isotopic signatures, δD , $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{17}\text{O}$ reached accuracy below 0.1‰ after less than one minute of integration time and the accuracy for the three signatures remained below 0.1 ‰ for 20-25 min of measurement time, which is the time within which we should perform a reference measurement with a standard water if we want to maintain an accuracy of the instrument below 0.1 ‰ (Figure 3.6).

The system has two polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) membrane blocks, one inside the instrument for pervaporating water as reference standard and the second one for collecting outside sample water. Water is vaporizing at the membrane if the pressure

Figure 3.6: Allan standard deviation corresponding to a five-hours dataset on ultrapure water at 2 sccm water vapor flow. The black dashed line represents the slope $1/\sqrt{N}$ corresponding to the evolution of white noise over time, with N the number of samples used for the average. The red dashed line indicates the time when precisions stay below 0.1 ‰.

behind the membrane is lower than the saturation pressure of the liquid water. We therefore decided to work at 8 mbar of pressure inside the measurement cell which is a good compromise for having relatively large spectral lines while ensuring the pervaporation of the water at low water temperature.

The instrument regularly measures the reference standard water to correct for instrumental drifts. Water is known as a sticky molecule. Although we treated internal surfaces with silcoloy coating to reduce surface interactions of water molecules, memory effect was still important. For this reason, we passivate the sample line with the new water sample before each measurement by performing several successive 2-s cleanings (1.5 s of full pumping high gas flow followed by 0.5 s of no pumping). This method provided faster sample-line washing with a memory factor of 0.02 after 100s of successive cleanings. This would mean that for a δD of 5 ‰ between one sample and the following, this memory factor would correspond to 0.1 ‰. Of course, the more the sample water has an isotopic composition similar to the reference water the smaller the memory effect between injected samples will be.

As the previous instrument for dissolved gas measurement, it is designed to fit in a titanium tube, allowing deployment down to 6000 m of depth (up today limited to 3000m by the PDMS membrane), it can run on batteries with an autonomy of ~ 12 h and it is equipped with SHDLS communication for telemetry propose.

The PhD work of Axel Wohleber was focused on the improvement of the instrument and its laboratory validation. During the PhD he managed to obtain more

Figure 3.7: Laboratory comparison between our SWIS instrument and the Picarro L2140i. Linear correlations were obtained with slopes of 0.986 ± 0.014 (SWIS) and 0.910 ± 0.012 (L2140i) for the δD (a), and 1.02 ± 0.058 (SWIS) and 0.958 ± 0.016 (L2140i) for the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (b). The blue dashed lines represent the theoretical slope values between the expected (mixing) and the measured values.

reproducible measurements with a precision of 0.3 ‰ (2σ) for all water isotopes with a 9-minute integration time (time to perform the sample and the reference measurement). He characterized the behaviors of the PDMS membranes we are using, investigated the way of reducing the membrane effect of the instrument, and estimated the isotopic fractionation of the reference water reservoir over time. He

also compared our sensor with a commercial instrument, the Picarro L2140i (Figure 3.7). The SWIS instrument demonstrated better linearity than the Picarro instrument in the isotopic range selected for the two studied isotopologues. The Picarro instrument provides a better precision (0.04 ‰, 2σ), on the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ measurement than the SWIS sensor (0.3 ‰, 2σ). Still, its accuracy would depend on how far away the isotopic value of the measurement sample is from the one of the reference sample. For making the accuracy close to the precision, a reference standard very close to the water to be analyzed (within 2 ‰ in the case of δD) is required or a non-linearity correction need to be applied to the measurement made with the commercial instrument. On the δD measurements, similar performances were achieved by the two instruments, but the SWIS instrument ensure a good linearity over the entire range studied (15 ‰) which was not the case for the L240i instrument. Furthermore, our development is more compact and designed for *in situ* measurements, providing a high temporal and spatial resolution even in very remote and difficult-to-access locations (e.g. beneath an ice shelf) and offering an easy way of measuring.

3.3.3 Field applications

We took advantage of the field campaign in the Black Sea in September 2021 to test the SWIS sensor in real conditions for the first time. The instrument was deployed for two vertical profiles at 50 and 700 m water depth and at shallow water over two horizontal transects. At that time, the accuracy of the system was not good enough, with 16 and 5.5 ‰ (1σ) for δD and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, respectively. After the campaign, we worked on improving the instrument's performance, and the work of Axel paid off. We then deployed the instrument in Lake Geneva twice (in October 2022 and July 2023), but unfortunately, during both campaigns, we had a problem with the vacuum pump, which was unable to maintain the required vacuum in the measurement cell. For this application, we use Scroll Lab's compact SVF pumps. Their compactness, low power consumption (5W), and low vibration level make them well-suited to in-situ applications, but unfortunately, they lack in reliability and require regular cleaning with ethanol (or similar alcohol) to remove the dust that accumulates in the scroll system.

The field campaign on the Fimbulisen Ice Shelf in Antarctica was scheduled for the austral summer of 2023/2024, with the instrument leaving our laboratory in October 2023. We therefore purchased two spare scroll pumps and kept our fingers crossed that the instrument would work properly in Antarctica. The Norwegian colleagues were planning to drill two boreholes in the Fimbulisen ice shelf, at ~ 1000 km from the Troll station, and we had the opportunity to deploy our instrument to capture the isotopic signal beneath the ice shelf for documenting the melting of the ice. Thanks to the fast measurement time of the sensor, we hoped to be able to capture a possible modulation of the melting signal due to the tide.

Neither I nor the PhD student could handle this field campaign, so in June 2023 we hired the engineer Julien Witwicky, and we trained him on the instrument over the summer. The choice of person was a difficult one: on the one hand, we

needed someone with good engineering skills, to solve any problems the instrument would have during the campaign, but more importantly, we needed someone who was used to extreme environments. For this campaign, a team of 11 people had to spend 40 days isolated in the field, in extreme conditions, sleeping in tents. In this type of campaign, participants had to cooperate, help each other out and be prepared to carry out joint tasks. Julien was winter-over at Concordia Station from September 2021 to February 2023, therefore he had good knowledge and experience of Antarctica, as well as good engineering skills.

The instrument arrived in the field in good condition, with the optical spectrometer aligned and operational as soon as it was unpacked. This was an excellent news, and gave us confidence that the instrument could operate properly in the borehole. The 40 days of the field campaign were busy with the preparation of the camp and drill operations, and the instrument could perform only two descents of a few hours into the borehole. During the first one, we had a communication problem through the cable, but also, the instrument was a bit heavy for the winch, and it made a free-fall into the borehole causing a misalignment of the optical system. After the deployment, the engineer managed to realign the system and they could perform the deployment again but only at the second site. The team managed to install a new cable, which was then used to moor the temperature sensors in the borehole. On this second deployment, the descent into the hole was smoother, but the regular impacts of the instrument against the hole walls were enough to misalign the optical spectrometer again.

Unfortunately, this field campaign was not a success for the SWIS instrument, but we have learned that we need to improve the immunity of the optical spectrometer to shock and vibration to make it suitable for this type of deployment. Nevertheless, we were able to collect water samples for laboratory analysis of water isotopes and noble gases, which we hope will provide information on the melting of the Fimbulisen Ice Shelf.

3.4 Conclusion and perspectives

Regarding the SubOcean instrument, the technology transfer to A2 Photonic Sensors is now finalized, with the first two instruments being constructed and sell. The laboratory prototype will still be used for ongoing projects, such as the EquipEx **TERRA FORMA** and the PEPR **FairCarboN**. In the frame of **TROPECOS** (within the FairCarbon project), the field campaign **PLUME** in Vietnam for measuring dissolved gas in Saigon River and the Mékong Delta and follow the continuum land-sea was performed in June 2024. During the campaign, we measured continuously and at high resolution the dissolved concentration of CO_2 , N_2O , CH_4 and $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$ for a better estimate of fluxes of GHGs into the atmosphere as well as a better understanding of the transport and transformation process at work. Last summer, the observation program **CARBOLéX**, led by D. Jezequel from INRAE-CARTELL started with the aim of estimating the fluxes of GHGs at the **LéXPLORER** plat-

form in Lake Geneva and its variability over the seasons, as well as understanding the fate of the presence of a methane peak at ~ 12 m of water depth. For this, the LSCE in Paris installed an Eddy Covariance instrument for measuring fluxes of CH_4 and CO_2 , and in May 2024 we installed two commercial instruments for long-term monitoring of dissolved CH_4 and CO_2 at 1m from the surface on a floating platform installed nearby the LÉXPLOREUR. We will punctually perform measurements with the floating chambers from INRAE-CARTELL and UNIL for having different methods for measuring fluxes (Eddy Covariance, diffusive estimation from dissolved gas measurements, and floating chambers). CTD measurement as well as discrete water samples will also be performed for the monitoring of the lake over the different seasons. The SubOcean could be used again for documenting the spatial variability of CH_4 on the lake at different seasons and stratification conditions.

In the future I would like to develop a novel method for measuring dissolved gas directly in the liquid, avoiding their extraction. This would lead to a more compact, simple, and hopefully reliable method for measuring dissolved gas. This could be done using evanescent wave detection coupled with an incoherent broadband direct absorption IR technique allowing to reduce costs and power consumption while accessing a larger source for multi-gas detection (ex. simultaneous detection of CH_4 , N_2O , and CO_2). For this project, I recently submitted a proposal to a call from CNRS Innovation, but unfortunately, it was not financed. I am therefore planning to resubmit the project to another call, and one possibility will be either an ANR or an ERC project.

Regarding the SWIS instrument, with the technical service, we would work on the improvement of the dumping system of the optical spectrometer. For the Antarctica field campaign, it was installed on silicone elastomers. The idea is to design a novel system to suspend the optical spectrometer for better immunity of the system to shocks and vibrations. Afterward, the instrument will be tested again at Geneva Lake, and we will use it for field deployment either from a vessel or a platform that would allow us an easier deployment for validating the functionality and the performance of the instrument in real conditions. The instrument could then be deployed for potential campaigns in the Arctic and Antarctica organized by colleagues from LOCEAN in Paris, Saint Andrews University and BAS in UK, NPI in Norway, AWI in Germany, and the University of Gothenburg in Sweden that may be scheduled in the next few years.

Applications to atmospheric chemistry

Contents

4.1	The Oxidative capacity at polar regions	43
4.2	The IBB-CEAS instrument for NO_x, CHOCHO and IO measurements	45
4.3	First applications of the IBB-CEAS instruments for understanding the NO_x chemistry at polar regions	46
4.3.1	New Estimation of the NO _x Snow-Sources on the Antarctic Plateau	46
4.3.2	Summer variability of the atmospheric NO ₂ :NO ratio at Dome C	49
4.3.3	Application of the IBB-CEAS instrument for understanding the chemistry in urban areas	52
4.3.4	Conversion of one of the two IBB-CEAS systems into an open-path analyzer	53
4.4	The attempt to LP-DOAS measurements for halogen oxide radicals	55
4.5	Conclusion and perspectives	58

4.1 The Oxidative capacity at polar regions

Southern regions present specificities that are highly relevant for studying the climate in connection with the atmospheric chemistry. These regions are very sensitive to the global climatic change: appearance and growth of the Antarctic ozone hole [Thomason & Peter 2006], rapid change of the sea-ice [Wolff *et al.* 2006], rapid increases of temperature [Muto *et al.* 2011], and changes in precipitation mass balance [DeConto & Pollard 2016]. Contrary to regions of the rest of the world, Antarctica is still considered as a pristine environment not yet influenced by predominant anthropogenic emissions and thus represents the last continental-size natural laboratory for studying natural emissions and processes.

Nevertheless, unexpected high levels of oxidants have been discovered in the continental interior as well as in the coastal regions, with atmospheric hydroxyl

radical (OH) concentrations as high as $4 \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ [Kukui *et al.* 2014]. These levels make the summer Antarctic boundary layer as oxidative as urban atmospheres, which was not expected for an atmosphere in such a remote environment.

It is now well established that the high reactivity of the summer Antarctic boundary layer results, in part, from the emissions of nitrogen oxides ($\text{NO}_x = \text{NO} + \text{NO}_2$) produced during photochemical release of nitrogen species from the snowpack [Jones *et al.* 2001]. The NO_x chemistry in the Antarctic plateau, however, remains not fully understood yet, particularly how the photochemical equilibrium between NO and NO_2 is affected by the snow surface emissions. Satellite measurements, even though integrated over the vertical column of the atmosphere, provide some important information on the distribution of halogen oxide radicals (XO; X = I, Br) in Antarctica, showing (i) a possible correlation with the presence of sea ice; (ii) both (but particularly BrO) show main emission in springtime; (iii) a possible presence of IO over the continent. Today, the sources of the halogen oxide radicals at these regions remain unclear and their role in particle formation requires deeper investigation. IO may nucleate via the self-reaction to form atmospheric particles that eventually grow into cloud condensation nuclei [Burkholder *et al.* 2004].

Precise and sensitive measurement of NO_x and XO are today still challenging because of the very low concentrations and high reactivity. Several techniques have been developed for their detection. Here below, I highlight a few of them, although this list is not exhaustive. Chemiluminescence Detection (CLD) [Navas *et al.* 1997], uses the chemiluminescence reaction occurring between O_3 and NO after the reduction of NO_2 into NO. It is widely used for air quality measurements with sensitivities better than 100 ppt [Ryerson *et al.* 2000]. Nevertheless, the interferences in the reduction of NO_2 to NO with other species (i.e. HONO and HNO_3) and the sensitivity to environmental conditions (temperature and humidity) leave uncertainties about absolute mixing ratio measurements.

The Multi-AXis Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (MAX-DOAS) technique has been used to measure XO and NO_2 by making use of the characteristic absorption features of gas molecules along a path in the open atmosphere [Hönninger *et al.* 2004]. Although MAX-DOAS is relatively simple to deploy, the data analysis makes it a complex approach for *in situ* field measurements due to the influence of clouds on the radiative transfer which alters the path length of light [Wittrock *et al.* 2004]. Long-path - differential optical absorption spectroscopy (LP-DOAS) offers an absorption measurement with a known optical path length but the technique still suffer from signal degradation due to the environmental conditions (clouds, rain and wind) which may hamper the measurements and affect either their accuracy or the sensitivity. Last point to consider is that, DOAS techniques are integrated over the long path leading to a limited spatial resolution [Nasse *et al.* 2019].

Compact, highly sensitive, and point-source measurements may be achieved using cavity-enhanced techniques such as cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) and cavity-enhanced absorption spectroscopy (CEAS) (Chapter 2). The potential of the CRDS for accurate, sensitive, and rapid measurements in a compact and transportable instrument has already been demonstrated with a sensitivity of 22 ppt for

NO₂ detection within 1 s of integration time [Fuchs *et al.* 2009]. OF-CEAS has also been proven for the detection of NO in the mid-IR regions with detection limits of 20 ppt within 1 s of integration time [Richard *et al.* 2018]. Mode-lock cavity-enhanced absorption spectroscopy (ML-CEAS) was also been developed during my first post-doc at LIPHy for the detection of BrO, IO and NO₂, with detection limits of 1 ppt in 1 min and 0.02 and 5 ppt in 5 min, respectively [Grilli *et al.* 2012b, Grilli *et al.* 2013].

Incoherent broadband - cavity-enhanced absorption spectroscopy (IBB-CEAS) is a robust, easy, high sensitive technique that has been used particularly for the detection of NO₃, NO₂, BrO, CHOCHO, etc. One of the best performance for the detection of NO₂ were performed by [Min *et al.* 2016] and [Liang *et al.* 2019] with a detection limit of 16 and 15 ppt in 1 min respectively (against 40 ppt for our development). In terms of long-term stability, Min *et al.* only had 100 sec while our work and the one of Liang *et al.* allow longer averages of 22 and 58 min respectively [Barbero *et al.* 2020].

4.2 The IBB-CEAS instrument for NO_x, CHOCHO and IO measurements

In September 2017 we started the development of two twins IBB-CEAS system on for measuring NO₂, CHOCHO and IO, and the second one that was equipped with a ozonizer for converting NO into NO₂ and measure their sum (NO_x). This development was conducted by the engineer Camille Blouzon and the PhD student Albane Barbero supervised by Joel Savarino and myself did their validation in the laboratory. A picture and schematic of the instrument is reported in Figure 4.1 and the instrument have been fully described in [Barbero *et al.* 2020]. As previously mentioned, with our setup we reached sensitivities comparable with previous works, with a minimum detectable absorption of $2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ achieved within ~ 22 min of total acquisition (meaning the acquisition of I and I₀ signal), and corresponding to a figure of merit of $1.8 \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1/2}$ per spectral element (2048 pixels). The effective optical path length provided by the optical cavity was 4.4 km and we used a low-cost uncooled diffraction grating spectrometer (Avantes ULS2048L).

The instrument was validated in the laboratory by comparing outdoor measurements of NO₂ for a few days against a commercial Chemiluminescence Detection system (CLD, Thermo Fisher™ 42i analyser) [Barbero *et al.* 2020]. We then investigated the conversion of NO to NO₂. For this we decided to make an ozone generator based on water electrolysis using commercial ozone microcells (INNOVATEC). This has several advantages: (i) the air sample is not diluted with a gas enriched in O₃ since the sample air flow to be analyzed works as carrier gas for flushing the ozone-enriched surface water; (ii) this generator does not produce nitrogen oxide impurities or unwanted oxidizing agents such as peroxides and do not require an oxygen gas bottle; (iii) the system is compact, (15 cm × 15 cm × 15 cm), offering a 200 cm³ water reservoir and several weeks of autonomy depending on the room temperature since the principal water loss is due to evaporation. The production of

Figure 4.1: (a) A picture of the instrument mounted on a 19 in., 3U rack-mount case. (b) Schematic of the instrument. The LED is protected by a cap in which a photodiode (PD) is monitoring its power. The light from the LED is collimated by lens L1 and injected into the cavity. The exiting light is then collimated with lens L2 and injected into the spectrometer. M1 and M2 are steering mirrors, and F is an optical filter. The gas line is composed of a pump, a pressure sensor P, a flowmeter FM and a proportional valve PV. At the inlet, a three-way two-position valve in PTFE, V, is used to switch between the sample and zero air. A manual PFA needle valve MV is used to fix the flow rate. An ozonizer can be inserted in the inlet line for NO_x measurements [Barbero *et al.* 2020].

O_3 is controllable by the amount of electrolytic cells used and the supplied current, offering a dynamic range of 0–50 ppm of O_3 for a 1 L min^{-1} total flow rate. Possible artifacts due to the presence of HONO or HO_2NO_2 for instance have been evaluated and described in detail in [Barbero *et al.* 2020]. The two instruments provided simultaneous measurement of NO_2 , IO, CHOCHO and O_3 with detection limits of 11, 0.3, 10 ppt, and 47 ppb (1σ) within 22 min of measurement, respectively. Detection limits for the indirect measurement of NO_x and NO are 10 and 21 ppt (1σ), respectively. Each instrument fits in a 19 in., 3U rack-mount case, for a weighs of 15 kg and a total electrical power consumption of $< 300\text{W}$.

4.3 First applications of the IBB-CEAS instruments for understanding the NO_x chemistry at polar regions

4.3.1 New Estimation of the NO_x Snow-Sources on the Antarctic Plateau

The two developed IBB-CEAS instruments were successfully deployed on two field campaigns at Concordia Station in Antarctica in 2018-19 and 2019-20 led by the PhD student A. Barbero. During this field campaign, two types of experiments were performed. The first one consisted of using flux chamber for studying the nitrate photolysis and therefore the NO_x emission from the snow in real condition but as well as in a controlled manner [Barbero *et al.* 2021].

Figure 4.2: (a) Schematic and (b) picture of the flux chamber experiment in the field. Further information in [Barbero *et al.* 2021]

Because photolysis of nitrate in snow occurs under UV radiation ($\lambda > 300$ nm with 305 nm the optimal wavelength), a chamber that will be transparent to UV is therefore essential for the experiment. The most UV-transparent material after glass is polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA). It is lighter than glass and therefore more practical to use in the field; however, it gets very brittle in cold environments. Within the different PMMAs, the Plexiglas Clear GS2458 GT (EBLA-GmbH Kunststofftechnik) provided the best transparency in the UV: $> 71\%$ of transmitted light for $\lambda > 300$ nm. The chamber was designed with dimensions of $70 \times 21 \times 21$ cm, giving a volume of 0.03 m^3 and a total surface area of 0.62 m^2 , providing enough NO_x production to be detected by the monitoring instruments.

Light attenuates quickly with depth in the snowpack following an exponential decrease. At Dome C, radiative transfer models predict a 95% loss of light in the snowpack after 50 cm depth at 305 nm wavelength (e.g., the actinic flux is effectively null below 50 cm). We therefore chose a depth of the chamber that would cover most of the the photic zone.

For each experiment, the chamber was filled with the desired snow and closed with clamps. It was then connected to a zero-air flow at the inlet and to the analytical instruments at the outlet (Figure 4.2). Different types of snow were collected with different estimated ages: 2 - 7 cm layer (3 - 10 months), 10 - 20 cm (1 - 2.5 years) 30 - 40 cm (3.5 - 4.5 years), 40 - 50 cm (4.5 - 6 years) as well as drifted snow. Snow was collated near the station and at 25 km South for more pristine samples. Other parameters such as O_3 , meteorological data, UV radiation were monitored during the experiment and NO_3^- concentration and snow density were measured prior and after each experiment.

Drifted snow was found to have up to 30 times more nitrate than the mean of all the rest of the snow samples, likely due to the blowing and stirring by the strong wind. The pristine snow from the 25 km site shows a rapid decrease in nitrate concentrations with depth, with less than 50 ng g^{-1} of nitrate remaining in

Figure 4.3: (a) The photolysis rate constants calculated for each experiment. Dark blue dot represents the drifted snow, red color the pristine snow samples, that is, 25 km South of Concordia station, and green color the local snow samples. Triangles represent the bottom layers (30–40 or 40–50 cm), squares the 10–20 cm layers, and diamonds the 2–7 cm layers. The mean $\pm 2\sigma$ is represented by the black diamond and the shaded area and has been calculated from the experiments, excluding the top layers due to: (1) the local top layer is suspected to be locally contaminated; (2) the $J(\text{NO}_3^-)$ of the pristine top layer was reconstructed due to missing data. (b) $J(\text{NO}_3^-)$ calculated for each experiment. The mean $\pm 2\sigma$ calculated from all the experiments is represented by the solid and dashed black lines.

the 30–40 cm layer. While local snow shows fairly uniform concentrations over the topmost 50 cm. The exponential decrease of nitrate concentration from the surface to depth is a common feature on the Antarctic plateau, determined by photolysis denitrification occurring in the photic zone, while the apparent homogeneous concentrations observed for the local snow may be due to site pollution as demonstrated by [Helmig *et al.* 2020]. A strong diurnal variability in the NO_x production from the snow was observed for each experiment, with a minimum around midnight and a maximum around local noon, following the daily UV radiation cycle.

A proportionality was observed between the nitrate concentrations contained in the snow samples and the amplitude of NO_x mixing ratios, and if we calculate the photolysis rate constant, $J(\text{NO}_3^-)$ we do not see any difference with respect to the type of snow with an exception for the local snow sample at 2–7 cm depth suspected to have been polluted by the station activities (Figure 4.3).

This result seems to confirm that the NO_x production is a process only driven by the amount of nitrate accessible to the photolysis. Because drifted snow (young) and snow collected in depth (old) possess the same photolysis rate under the same incident light flux despite the radically different nitrate concentrations, we can reasonably conclude that the nitrate present in the snow samples has the same accessibility to photolysis. This is in line with the observation of [Bock *et al.* 2016] and with the mechanism responsible for the incorporation of nitrate in the snow at cold sites such as Dome C proposed by [Chan *et al.* 2018] and disagree with the study of [Davis *et al.* 2008] and [Meusinger *et al.* 2014] which proposed two nitrate domains: an easy photolabile nitrate fraction (i.e., adsorbed on the surface of ice) and a more

difficult to successfully photolyze fraction (i.e., incorporated within the ice crystal lattice).

By performing each measurement over several days, we surprisingly notice a general exponential decrease in NO_x mixing ratio over time [Barbero *et al.* 2021]. This cannot be due to the denitrification of the snow, since the measured decrease of NO₃⁻ in the chamber cannot justify this (it represents on average 0.12 ± 0.01 % of the initial amount of nitrate). We also performed nitrate measurement every 2 cm of depth in the flow chamber after the experience and we do not see any difference in the amount of nitrate, so this transient regime cannot be justified by the depletion in nitrate on the first layer of snow. The possibility that HNO₃ molecules may have been adsorbed at the walls of the chamber during the experiment can be disclaimed by the fact that the difference in nitrate concentration in the snow before and after the experiment cannot justify this hypothesis. However, the adsorption of nitric acid (HNO₃) on the walls of the chamber during the installation of the experiment may be the explanation. Zhu *et al.* determined the absorption cross-sections of surface-adsorbed HNO₃, in the 290–330 nm region using CRDS [Zhu *et al.* 2008]. They found that the HNO₃-adsorbed absorption cross-section at 305 nm was 700 times higher than the absorption cross-section of HNO₃ in the gas phase. This could therefore be the cause of the transitory regime that we observed, but it remains an hypothesis and it would need further studies to be confirmed.

Daily summer NO_x fluxes at Dome C were estimated to be $(4.3 \pm 1.2) \times 10^8$ molecules cm⁻² s⁻¹ over the observation period if all NO_x were removed from the snowpack. This is 1.5 – 7 times lower than what has been estimated in previous studies at Dome C based on atmospheric gradient measurements, which could be explained by the presence of strong recycling and inter-annual variability of the snowpack and atmospheric conditions at a single site. By extrapolating our flux chamber observations, an annual snow-source NO_x budget of 0.017 ± 0.003 Tg N y⁻¹ of nitrogen was calculated for the entire Antarctica. For comparison, according to the European Environment Agency (EEA) data, the annual NO_x emissions of France are ~ 0.4 Tg N y⁻¹.

4.3.2 Summer variability of the atmospheric NO₂:NO ratio at Dome C

During the same field campaign, atmospheric measurements of NO_x were also conducted in December and January with the same IBB-CEAS instruments described above. An expected diurnal cycle was observed corresponding to the development and collapse of the polar boundary layer. Average values of NO₂:NO ratio of 1.3 ± 1.1 (1σ) in December and 0.40 ± 0.4 (1σ) in January were observed. As visible from Figure 4.4 the ratio is higher at the beginning of the seasons and decreases over time. While the ratio found in January matches with the value predicted by Leighton’s photochemical equilibrium (both simple, which only considers NO_x and O₃ and the extended one that also includes RO_x) [Barbero *et al.* 2022], at the beginning of the seasons this ratio is higher and no longer matches the one theoretically expected

(Figure 4.4). The HYSPLIT 5-day backward trajectories ran at 4 different times of day show a drastic change in the air mass origin, with the one at the end of the measurement period affected by marine origins (east coast of Antarctica), and this can explain the sudden drop of O₃ observed at this period.

Figure 4.4: **(top)** Dark blue left-hand scale: mixing ratios (pptv) of NO₂ (blue), NO (black), and NO_x (cyan) and red right-hand scale: NO₂:NO ratio. The signals are 6-hour running means (solid) on top of one hour means signals (dashed). **(bottom)** Green left-hand scale: mixing ratio of O₃ (ppbv) and orange right-hand scale: UV radiations (W m²) measured with a broadband radiometer, spectral range 305 - 385 nm. The signals of O₃ are 6-hour running mean (solid) on top of one one-hour mean signal (dashed). Each day is marked with vertical black lines at 00:00 local time (LT).

The polar boundary layer plays an important role in the mixing of the atmosphere at Dome C. With the aim of deciphering the mechanisms occurring at Dome C during our observations, we decided to account for the dilution effect due to the diurnal variation of the polar boundary layer and express concentrations as the total number of molecules within the boundary layer. We also calculated the production of ozone, P_{O_3} in molecules s⁻¹, as the NO₂ production rate from the reaction $RO_2 + NO \rightarrow NO_2 + RO$ and $HO_2 + NO \rightarrow NO_2 + OH$, as reported by [Kukui *et al.* 2014] which appears substantially different from the observed O₃ variations (dO_3/dt). In the lower panels of Figure 4.5 are reported the deviations of the observed ratio ($NO_2:NO_{obs}$) from the simple and extended Leighton's equilibria ($\Delta NO_2:NO_{sim} = NO_2:NO_{obs} - NO_2:NO_{simple}$ and $\Delta NO_2:NO_{ext} = NO_2:NO_{obs} - NO_2:NO_{extended}$). The NO₂:NO ratio seems to follow Leighton's equilibrium in January and as NO does not evolve between the two periods of observation, it highlights the necessity of an additional primary source of NO₂ other than the conversion of NO to NO₂ by

reactions with O_3 and radicals species (XO , RO_x , HO_2).

Figure 4.5: (a) and (b) 3-hour running mean (solid lines) $\pm 1 \sigma$ (thin dashed lines) of the diurnal cycles of NO (black), NO_x (cyan) and NO_2 (blue) total number of molecules in a column of $1 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ H}_{PBL} [\text{cm}]$ (top panels) and $\text{NO}_2:\text{NO}$ ratio (bottom panels) observed (red) and equilibrium's calculations (simple Leighton in grey, extended Leighton in black) for December and January respectively. (c) and (d) represent the 3-hour running mean (solid lines) $\pm 1 \sigma$ (thin dashed lines) of the diurnal cycle of the total number of ozone molecules in a column of $1 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ cm} \times 1 \text{ H}_{PBL} [\text{cm}]$ (green), the O_3 variations, $d\text{O}_3/dt$, in molecules s^{-1} and the ozone production, P_{O_3} in molecules s^{-1} calculated from the total number of RO_2 and NO molecules (top panels); the bottom panels represent the differences between $\text{NO}_2:\text{NO}$ observed and $\text{NO}_2:\text{NO}$ calculated ($\Delta\text{NO}_2:\text{NO}$) in grey for simple Leighton and $\Delta\text{NO}_2:\text{NO}$ in black for extended Leighton.

To explain our data set, we considered various hypotheses as discussed in [Barbero *et al.* 2022]. We investigated if the presence of halogenated radicals explains our data. To answer this question we calculated the amount of XO needed in December to justify the measured $\text{NO}_2:\text{NO}$ ratio. A daily mean average of XO of

17 pptv were estimated, with a peak of 64 pptv at 11:00 LT. If such high levels of XO were present, it would have been observed by MAX-DOAS during the OPALE campaign as XO is suspected to be mainly BrO at Dome C [Frey *et al.* 2015]. Additionally, such high levels of XO would induce some fast destruction of O₃, which was not observed either, and finally, NO levels would have been lower in December than in January. Therefore, the assumption of an additional conversion of NO to NO₂ through XO or RO_x seems insufficient to explain the observations, and only the increased production of NO₂ from primary sources of NO₂ by a factor of 2 may justify the NO₂ excess observed in December and not in January.

Therefore we investigated the hypothesis of a larger NO_x sources from the snowpack at the beginning of the photolytic season (December) with respect to a later time (January). The average nitrate concentration in surface snow (a few millimetres) is 991 ± 341 ppbw (parts per billion by weight or ng g⁻¹) (median 931–70 samples) in December and 588 ± 248 ppbw (median 558–65 samples) in January, respectively. This ~ 40 % difference between December and January at the surface of the snowpack is significantly large. Since 2015 we are running an automatic snow tower experiment with measurement of NO_x and O₃ at different depths in the snow [Helmig *et al.* 2020]. Although the experiment was not running during the 2019–2020 campaign, we had previous data that show a ~ 50 % higher concentration of NO_x in December than in January, particularly in the morning, which is coherent with the difference measured on the nitrate concentration, and it seems a valid hypothesis to explain the deviation from the photo-chemical equilibrium observed in the morning during the early photolysis season. To further reinforce this hypothesis, the solar zenith angle (SZA) also shows a substantial difference between December and January, with an asymmetry at early time of the day in December which would be consistent with a stronger solar flux at this period and therefore a stronger nitrate photolysis. From our calculations, it appears that a 5% difference in the SZA in the morning could lead to an excess of up to 5 times the NO₂:NO ratio when at steady state [Barbero *et al.* 2022].

In January 2024, Albane received the André Prudhomme prize organized by Météo et Climat with the support of Météo-France for the best doctoral thesis defended in the fields of meteorology, atmospheric physics and chemistry, paleoclimatology, climatology (including oceanographic aspects).

4.3.3 Application of the IBB-CEAS instrument for understanding the chemistry in urban areas

The IBB-CEAS instruments were used in the frame of the PhD thesis of Sarah Albertin supervised by J. Savarino and S. Bekki. Her work aimed to investigate the mechanisms of formation of nitrate aerosols in urban polar and alpine environments in particular during winter time, to identify the principal NO_x sources and reaction paths. For this, Sarah used the isotopic composition of atmospheric nitrate and NO₂ together with concentration measurements of NO_x and O₃ in order to understand the chemistry at work. For the NO_x measurements, we therefore used the IBB-

CEAS instruments together with an OF-CEAS spectrometer developed at LIPhy for direct measurement of NO [Richard *et al.* 2018]. In February 2021 we went for one week field campaign in Chamonix-Mont-Blanc (France). The field campaign provided a unique dataset to further investigate the NO_x chemistry in urban environment during winter and conclude that vehicle exhaust is the main contributor to NO_x emissions at the studied site. More information on this work can be found in [Albertin *et al.* 2024]

4.3.4 Conversion of one of the two IBB-CEAS systems into an open-path analyzer

This development was conducted in the frame of the one-month (August 2023) Internship of Filip Pastierovic from the Comenius University Bratislava (Slovakia). IBB-CEAS instruments were originally designed to be able, at some point, to perform open-path measurements in order to provide local quantitative measurements of IO, which is a highly reactive species with a short lifetime. To do so, we need to make some changes and particularly separate the optics components from the electronic parts. This is important because the optical part will be placed outside

Figure 4.6: The IBB-CEAS setup modified for open-path measurement. Here the optical components were separated from the rest of the setup allowing the latter to be placed in a protected place while the optical path is exposed to environmental conditions. The air coming from a membrane pump is pushed through a flow meter, FM, to a Zero Air generator and to a manual valve, MV, for controlling the flow. The flow is then split in three parts: one going at the center of the cell tube and the other two used for purging the HR mirrors. Details about the rest of the electronic components can be found in [Barbero *et al.* 2020].

and exposed to environmental conditions and for instance in marine environments,

we want to prevent the salt from damaging the electrical components. Therefore, we placed the optical part in a second rack case, and we made the wiring for placing the two boxes at $\sim 2\text{m}$ distance from each-other. In the optical part, we added an automated translation stage that moves a rigid tube inside and outside the optical path inside the cavity. This allows to regularly inject zero air to measure without the presence of absorption (I_0). The zero air is generated using the same filtering system (TEKRAN 90-25360-00 Analyzer Zero Air Filter) and using the same diaphragm pump to push zero air into the tube (and originally used to draw air from the cavity). The air enters at the center of the tube, and escapes at the ends. Zero air is also used to continuously flush the two high-reflective mirrors on the cavity to prevent them from getting dirty during long-term deployment. A total flow of 4 L min^{-1} STP is used, $\sim 1.5\text{ L min}^{-1}$ at each mirror and $\sim 1\text{ L min}^{-1}$ for flushing the cavity. A schematic of the setup is reported in Figure 4.6. The optical box has a 70 cm^2 aperture at the front and air circulation is ensured by the fan system used for dissipating the heating of the LED assembly with an airflow of $\sim 600\text{ L min}^{-1}$. In Figure 4.7 is reported a comparison between close-path and open-path setups.

Figure 4.7: Comparison between close-path and open-path outdoor measurements conducted in Grenoble using the two IBB-CEAS instruments. The sample inlet of the close-path system was placed close to the open-path instrument.

This was conducted in Grenoble, on outdoor air nearby IGE. The optical box of the open-path instrument was left outside, while the close-path instrument was inside the building, and a 2.5-m long $1/4''$ PFA tubing was used to sample the air near the open-path instrument. On the comparison of the NO_2 signals, we can see that both instruments captured well the morning and evening peaks related to the traffic in

the town. Some discrepancy in the peak height is sometimes observed but the two data showed a good correlation ($R^2 = 0.93$) with a 6% discrepancy in the correlation slope. IO and CHOCHO signal reported a degradation of the detection limit by a factor of three while operating in open-path conditions, and while IO stays around zero values for both systems, CHOCHO signal reported a positive offset of about 200 ppt in open-path configuration. The reasons for this offset have not yet been identified. We have to say that in urban air, NO_2 concentration are very strong and they may cause artifacts on the background measurements of IO and CHOCHO. In a more remote environment, when IO and CHOCHO will be of interest, the level of NO_2 on unpolluted air masses will probably be < 1 ppb, which will facilitate the measurements of the other species. A publication describing this open path development and its validation is ongoing with an implication of the student F. Pastierovic on the writing of the manuscript.

4.4 The attempt to LP-DOAS measurements for halogen oxide radicals

During my first post-doc (2010-2013) we developed an optical spectrometer based on the ML-CEAS for measuring BrO, IO and NO_2 in the atmosphere. This development was based on the injection of a femtosecond laser into an optical cavity [Grilli *et al.* 2012b]. During a test field campaign at Roscoff station in 2011 we tested different lengths of PFA tube at the inlet on an atmospheric signal of ~ 1 - 2 ppt of IO (the detection limit was 0.02 ppt, so we had a relatively high S/R ratio on the measurement) and we did not observed any decreasing in the measured concentration of IO while going from 1 to 10 m of PFA tube. We also changed the laser power using the Acoustic Optic Modulator (AOM) and no changes in the IO measurement were observed. We therefore concluded that IO was efficiently transported in our sample inlet. In the Austral Summer of 2012-13 we performed a field campaign at the Antarctic Station of Dumont D'Urville in the East Coast as scheduled by the project. The level of IO measured was very low, ranging from the detection limit (0.04 ppt) to a maximum value of 0.15 ppt and the measurements of BrO were within the noise of the instrument (2 ppt).

Afterward, we reconsidered the fact that the halogen oxides may not be efficiently transported in the sample inlet because during our test we may have been biased by the fact that IO can also be generated in the measuring cell. In fact, I_2 or other RI precursors can be photolyzed by the laser radiation at 440 nm and form IO by reaction with O_3 . At the beginning of the PhD thesis of A. Barbero we decided to go to the IASC atmospheric chamber in Cork (Ireland) to conduct experiments in a controlled environment. The instrument was connected to the chamber where the halogen oxide radicals were produced. Unfortunately, the quantum yield of the photolysis in the chamber was not well known, therefore we played with the air flow on our instrument going from 1 to 17 L min^{-1} . Increasing the flow, we observed an increase in the concentration of the radicals (up to 400 ppt for instance for BrO)

Figure 4.8: The experimental setup of the LP-DOAS system we developed. The frequency doubled (with a BBO, Beta Barium Borate crystal) femtosecond laser was filtered from the fundamental radiation with three dichroic mirrors, DM, sent to a telescope for making the beam about 1" diameter and sent at the retro-reflector placed few kilometers away. The light coming back is collected and sent to the grating spectrometer described in [Grilli *et al.* 2012b]. SM are stirring mirrors.

but the measured concentration continued to increase with flow, meaning that 100% efficiency was not reached even flushing the inlet tube at 17 L min^{-1} .

We therefore decided to transform the ML-CEAS instrument into a Long Path - Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (LP-DOAS) instrument. By sending the laser radiation to a retro-reflector placed few km away from the instrument and analyzing the light reflected with the grating spectrometer we could have the few km optical path length needed for achieving the required sensitivity while avoiding the problem of the transport of the reactive radical inside a measurement cell. The experimental setup is described in Figure 4.8. Because of the turbulence (and perhaps in part the mechanical instability of the system), the beam at the retro-reflector needs to have a beam waist of at least 50 cm, and only a portion of the sent light is reflected back (the retro-reflector is 5 cm in diameter). 30 mW of optical power was enough to have a signal close to saturation with a minimum integration time of 12 ms at the CCD (Charge-Coupled Device).

Although we successfully went through a series of challenges with this development, including the alignment of the beam at the retro-reflector placed 5 km away, the recorded spectra were strongly modulated by parasite optical fringes and structures that were not related to absorption features. In Figure 4.9 we report an example of spectrum that we obtained with 8 ppb of NO_2 . In black is reported the absorption signal, in red is the fit of the absorption of NO_2 , in orange is the baseline that already accounted for three strong optical fringes that were identified at specific

Figure 4.9: A typical spectrum was obtained with the LP-DOAS approach using a femtosecond laser and a diffraction grating spectrometer. The spectrum was recorded during a test field campaign at Roscoff station (France) in 2018 over an optical path length of ~ 8 km. The fit routine retrieved 7.8 ppb of NO_2 and 0.5 ppt of IO. For this, modulation frequencies were added on the baseline accounting for optical fringes (orange line), but a strong structure of the same amplitude of the absorption is still visible on the residual (blue line) causing a strong degradation of the sensitivity of the technique.

frequencies and in blue is the residual that is still strongly structured. To achieve ppt level detection for IO and BrO we should be able to detect NO_2 with a sensitivity of 0.25 ppb. We therefore decided to further work to improve the sensitivity of the system. In 2020 and 2021 two master students M. Scwharz, who did a 3-month M1 internship in Physics, and S. Arioli who did a 6-month M2 internship in Earth Sciences, worked on different strategies for improving the detection limit of this spectrometer. During these internships, we used single-mode fibers before injecting the light into the spectrometer for spatially cleaning the laser beam. But we were confronted to high power losses in the coupling due to the multi-mode character of the laser beam ($M^2 = 27$) coming back from the retro-reflector. We then used multi-mode fibers, but we had to deal with strong mode structures generated inside the optical fiber that were still present despite the efforts for making mode-mixing in the fiber. The detection limit we obtained for the LP-DOAS setup we developed was unfortunately not enough for detecting atmospheric levels of either NO_2 , IO and BrO in the atmosphere.

4.5 Conclusion and perspectives

Regarding the IBB-CEAS instruments, they are today operational and we are planning further field campaigns. The next one will be at the sub-Antarctic Amsterdam Island. This is in the frame of the IPEV CAPOXI project, led by J. Savarino, that aims to compare the chemistry at (i) Concordia, on the Antarctic plateau where the chemistry related to the snow-pack dominates, (ii) Dumont D'Urville, on the Antarctic coast, where we are expecting influences due to the snow-pack, the sea-ice as well as the open sea, and (iii) Amsterdam Island where the chemistry will be dictated by the presence of the sea and sea-salt aerosols. This campaign at Amsterdam Island will take place this year. I will lead the installation of the two IBB-CEAS instruments (one in close-path and the other one in the open-path configuration) for measuring NO_2 , IO and CHOCHO and the OF-CEAS instrument developed at LIPhy for direct measurements of NO [Richard *et al.* 2018]. The instruments will be installed in November and will acquire data continuously over a few months. At Amsterdam Island, in the frame of the project Obs4Clim, the team of K. Sellegri at LAMP in Clermont-Ferrand is installing facilities to measure submicron size distribution, total concentration, and diffusion properties of aerosols. This, coupled with our measurements of IO, NO_x and CHOCHO would provide an interesting dataset to investigate more closely the aerosols nucleation processes at this site. After this campaign, we will focus on the chemistry at DDU in order to complete the study planned by the CAPOXI project. In the future, the instruments could be further improved in terms of sensitivity by installing higher reflectivity mirrors as the one used in [Min *et al.* 2016], which will allow us to increase the optical path length by a factor of 4. This would also reduce the amount of light transmitted through the cavity, therefore if the integration time would increase above 1 min, then replacing the grating spectrometer with one with a cooled CCD would decrease the dark noise. The dark noise of the current uncooled Avantes spectrometer reaches 5% of the total signal at the CCD within 1 min of integration time, while with a cooled (-70°C) CCD this noise will be 10 times lower.

The ML-CEAS technique developed during my first post-doc could be extended to other species and particularly to the OH radical at 308 nm. The finesse of the optical cavity will be limited by losses due to Rayleigh scattering, which at this wavelength in air at 25°C and 1 atmosphere are $1.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{cm}^{-1}$. For a cavity length of 2 m, this would correspond to 2.4×10^{-4} losses per passage. With HR mirrors with similar losses (corresponding to a maximum achievable reflectivity of $\sim 99.975\%$), an optical path length of ~ 8 km is reachable, which is close to the one used for IO detection (10 km). According to the manufacturer, such a high reflectivity can be achieved with a transmission of ~ 40 ppm. For IO we proved a detection limit of 0.04 ppt or 1×10^6 molecules cm^{-3} within 5 minutes of integration time, and because OH absorption cross-sections are more than six times stronger than the one for IO, for OH radical we should achieve a detection limit of 2×10^5 molecules cm^{-3} (or 0.008 ppt), which is well adapted for its detection in atmospheric chemistry studies. In collaboration with the ICARE laboratory in Orleans and in

the frame of the [EquipEx Obs4Clim](#) we are going to develop a system for measuring the OH radical in the HELIOS atmospheric chamber. Because of the problems encountered with the reactive species, the measurement in a close cavity should be avoided. Inspired from what we recently did with the IBB-CEAS, we propose a detection with an open-path setup. Previously, we were working with the cavity comb closely matching the laser comb. Here, each tooth of the laser comb goes into resonance at slightly a different time but still with the same speed, which ensures that the whole laser spectrum is transmitted by the cavity with no distortion. However, in an open path configuration, this close matching between the two combs may be difficult to maintain over time due to the presence of turbulence and thermal and mechanical instabilities. Therefore, we would mismatch in propose the two combs reaching a number of groups of mode well above the number of spectral elements at the spectrometer so that this "beating" pattern formed by the fact that modes are getting in resonance and off-resonance while going from left to right on the spectrum would not be resolved by the spectrometer. Here, a frequency modulation of either the laser or the cavity comb should not be required, but it could help smoothing the transmitted signal. The measurement of the photon lifetime in the measurement cell will be performed by phase-shift measurement rather than with a ring-down time technique which will be more adapted to this approach.

The development of the LP-DOAS technique has not been left aside. We think that the optical fringes forming a dynamic pattern noise on the spectrum are related to the wavefront aberration caused by atmospheric turbulence and thermal blooming. This pattern noise appeared on our spectrum because of the wavelength dispersion made by the grating spectrometer, but in a detection system where we do not need to disperse the beam in frequency, this pattern noise should not occur. This should be the case for a multi-heterodyne detection in a dual comb configuration or for a detection using a Fourier transform spectrometer. For this reason, with colleagues from the LIPhy in Grenoble and the University of Rennes we continue to work on the topic. In Rennes, L. Rutkowski developed a Fourier transform spectrometer coupled with a frequency comb laser source [[Rutkowski *et al.* 2018](#)], and the colleagues at LIPhy are currently working on a dual-comb spectroscopy system but using a single frequency comb laser. The idea here consists of periodically switching the comb frequency repetition rate so that the light traveling the long path comes back with a delay long enough to interfere with the light of the comb that has propagated on a much shorter path length. The two beams will then have different repetition rates. The proof-of-concept has been published in 2018 by Carlson *et al.* and achieved the detection of HCN in a cell with comb mode resolution using a 3 km long fiber as a delay line [[Carlson *et al.* 2018](#)]. In our case we would replacing the fiber by an open path propagation over few kilometers.

In the future, this LP-DOAS technique could be coupled with a drone to perform vertical profiles of atmospherically important species. Drones are limited by the weight of the instrumentation that they can carry. The advantage of LP-DOAS approach is that the instrumentation can stay on the ground, and only the retro-reflector, which weighs ~ 100 gr, will be mounted on the drone. The challenge of

the measurement will be to track the drone's movements from the ground, requiring a feedback loop to keep the laser alignment during the vertical profile. Here, the Fourier transform detection will be more adapted than the dual-comb approach since the latter would require to adapt the time of the switch of the repetition rate of the laser to the distance of the drone to the ground instrument. This vertical profiling will be used to study the distribution of reactive species in the atmospheric boundary layer, as well as to produce vertical profiles above Volcanic plumes, which are more difficult and risky to access by other means (helicopters or planes).

Applications to ice core sciences

Contents

5.1 Atmospheric CO₂ in ice cores to study carbon cycle - climate feedback	61
5.2 Development of a CO₂ and $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ spectrometer	63
5.3 Development of a new dry extraction method	66
5.4 Conclusion and perspectives	71

5.1 Atmospheric CO₂ in ice cores to study carbon cycle - climate feedback

A better understanding of future climate relies heavily on our ability to characterize its coupling with the carbon cycle and to estimate the balance of both anthropogenic and natural carbon dioxide emissions. This coupling is complex because of the constant exchanges and feedbacks between the ocean, the terrestrial biosphere and the atmosphere. These exchanges take place on time scales ranging from hundreds to thousands of years and therefore require high-resolution paleoclimate records. The EPICA Dome C deep-ice drilling has made it possible to reconstruct the evolution of atmospheric CO₂ over the last 800,000 years (Bereiter et al., 2015). In recent years, higher-resolution measurements (~ 300 years resolution) have been carried out to characterize variability on millennial timescales and better understand the causes of these rapid variations. The latest works were carried out in the frame of the PhD thesis of J. Shin (2015-2019), which I co-supervised with J. Chappellaz in collaboration with the University of Bern (Switzerland). During her PhD, Jinhwa performed high-quality measurements in terms of both accuracy and time resolution on the penultimate glaciation (Marine Isotopic Stage 6, MIS6, 190–135 kyr B.P., Figure 5.1) [Shin *et al.* 2020]. The colleagues from Bern collected a similar dataset for the MIS11 and MIS10 period (330-450 kyr B.P.) [Nehrbass-Ahles *et al.* 2020].

This research reveals the existence of CO₂ pulses (also noticed as Carbon Dioxide Jumps, CDJs) spanning from one to five centuries, occurring not only during ice ages but also during warm periods. Their amplitude remains relatively moderate, on the order of 10 ppm, whereas the increase in atmospheric CO₂ due to human activity over the last 200 years has already reached over 130 ppm. Furthermore, the current rate of CO₂ increase is 10 times more rapidly than the faster of the pulses observed

Figure 5.1: High-resolution atmospheric CO₂ measurements from the EPICA Dome C ice core during the penultimate glaciation conducted during the PhD thesis of J. Shin and showing a strong correlation with temperature variations (illustrated here by ice isotopic content, D, in gray) [Shin *et al.* 2020]

in our studies. The mechanism behind these CO₂ jumps remains so far unknown, and may be related to a combination of factors including ocean circulation, changing of wind patterns, and terrestrial processes. E. Legrain, PhD student in our group (2020-2023) under the supervision of E. Capron and F. Parrenin, continued this work, investigating also at a high-resolution an intermediate period, MIS7 (260 – 190 kyr B.P.), and conducting the same analysis for identifying CDJs. This recent study submitted for publication this year in *Nature Geoscience* revealed seven new CDJs and highlighted how 18 of the 22 CDJs identified over the past 500,000 years occurred under a context of high obliquity (tilt of the Earth’s rotational axis). High obliquity leads to more pronounced seasonal contrasts, with warmer summers and colder winters in both hemispheres. This has an impact on the extent of ice cover, particularly in polar regions. Although winters were colder, the increased summer melting typically had a more significant impact on the overall ice balance. A lower ice cover decreases the albedo effect, leading to more heat absorption and further warming. This warming can enhance the melting of permafrost, releasing stored carbon in the form of CO₂ and CH₄ into the atmosphere. Obliquity also affects oceanic currents and stratification: during periods of high obliquity, increased stratification of the ocean can limit the mixing of surface waters with deeper, carbon-enriched waters, affecting the ocean’s ability to absorb and store carbon. Warmer summers promote increased plant growth, leading to higher photosynthetic activity and greater carbon uptake by plants but also high microbial activity in soils, leading to higher rates of soil respiration and release of CO₂. In this work, new simulations performed with an Earth system model of intermediate complexity point toward both the continental biosphere and the Southern Ocean as the two main carbon sources during these rapid events. Notably, the continental biosphere appears to be

the obliquity-dependent CO₂ source for CDJs connected to Heinrich events (massive iceberg breakups in the North Atlantic Ocean during the Quaternary ice ages). Therefore, long-term external forcing seems to have a direct impact on past abrupt variations in atmospheric CO₂, and the CO₂ trend in the current high obliquity phase could be affected by additional atmospheric CO₂ contribution from natural sources.

For further investigating the reasons for those CDJs and more in general of the past changes in atmospheric CO₂ and their link with the climate, the isotopic signature, δ¹³CO₂, is an indispensable marker, allowing to gain details in the understanding of exchanges between reservoirs, and thus identify the mechanisms involved. For this reason, we are currently developing a new optical spectrometer for the measurement of atmospheric CO₂ and δ¹³CO₂. This instrument is based on a direct absorption spectroscopy technique and it is described in the following section. We are also currently working on a new dry extraction method for producing air samples from ice core for molecules with high solubility in water such as CO₂ and N₂O.

5.2 Development of a CO₂ and δ¹³CO₂ spectrometer

In recent years, colleagues from LIPhy have been working on various developments for CO₂ isotopic measurement. In the near-infrared, at 1.6 μm, the simultaneous, high-precision measurement of δ¹³C and Δ¹⁷O has been validated for pure CO₂ samples, with applications for marine sediment analysis. The technique used is called V-Shaped Cavity Optical Feedback - Cavity Ring Down Spectroscopy (VCOF-CRDS) and uses a sub-kHz laser source of high-precision CRDS measurements (Chapter 2). This compensates for the fact that absorption lines are weak at this wavelength, reducing measurement noise to a few 10⁻¹² cm⁻¹ [Stoltmann *et al.* 2017] and even below (few 10⁻¹³ cm⁻¹) today. These extraordinary performances are achieved using a complex optical method, which requires significant knowledge of optics and laser spectroscopy for its use. In 2012-2015 the same research team also explored the mid-infrared spectral region, in which fundamental CO₂ transitions are available, with intensities almost six orders of magnitude greater (Figure 2.2). This approach used OFCEAS technology, the same technique mentioned in Chapter 3 for the measurement of dissolved gases. Unfortunately, laboratory tests revealed a technological limitation related to a pronounced effect of optical saturation of very ("too") intense absorption lines, due to the high intracavity optical power induced by the resonator. Here, because of the strong rovibrational transitions, the molecules present in the measurement cell can be all pushed to the excited state, and because at low gas pressure, the deexcitation of the molecule due to collisions is weak, and there are basically no more molecules in the ground state to absorb the light. This is called optical saturation, and cause a bias in the measurement of the concentration of the molecules and therefore their isotopic ratio. The group of L. Emmenegger at EMPA laboratory in Switzerland developed a new optical spectrom-

Figure 5.2: A picture of the experimental setup under development for measuring CO_2 and $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$. A mono-block aluminum double cell was designed for measuring simultaneously the sample and the reference gas and gain some immunity to thermal drifts. The laser is going back and forward inside the 20-cm long cell for a total optical absorption path length of 40 cm.

eter for measuring $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ in ice cores [Bereiter *et al.* 2020]. They also worked in the mid-infrared region, but using a multipass cell to obtain an optical path of 30 m. The low optical power of the laser in the measurement cell reduces the effects of line saturation. But because the cell volume remains relatively large (160 mL) and the amount of air in an ice sample is limited (about 1 mL STP in 10 g of ice) they have to work at low pressure (5 mbar). Our saturation calculations suggest that their system should still be in the saturation regime at these pressure conditions. This means that fluctuations in laser power intensity and a change in the bulk gas, which would result in a different deexcitation efficiency of the excited molecules, could be a source of significant artifacts in the isotopic measurements. Nevertheless, they can achieve a remarkable accuracy of 0.04 ‰ within a few minutes of measurement making rigorous calibrations with standard gas with different isotopic compositions and signatures.

By going from a cell pressure of 5 to 50 mbar we gain a factor of seven on the intensity of the absorption line, we then will considerably lose sensitivity shortening the optical path length from 30 m to 40 cm, but multipass cells are known for their weaknesses linked to optical fringes, leading to a degradation of the sensitivity of the technique. Therefore we decided to take the challenge of achieving similar performance using a direct absorption technique, with the advantage of reducing by a factor of 100 the risk of optical saturation and making the detection using a simple and robust technique. A simulation of the absorption spectrum of 200 ppm CO_2 at 50 mbar in air at 4.355 μm shows intensities of 1×10^{-3} and $6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $^{12}\text{CO}_2$ and $^{13}\text{CO}_2$, respectively (corresponding to 4% and 2.4% light absorption over

a 40 cm optical path). A direct-absorption optical system well designed to minimize optical fringe effects (avoid transmission optics, using super-polished optics with anti-reflective coatings, etc.) is capable of achieving a transmission measurement noise of less than 10^{-4} . Over a 40 cm optical path, this corresponds to an absorption of $2.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, and a signal-to-noise ratio for ¹²CO₂ and ¹³CO₂ lines above 300. Given that line surfaces are obtained over a spectrum made up of several spectral elements, measurement accuracy is improved by the square root of this number). A precision of 0.5 ‰ is therefore possible on a single spectrum. By averaging spectra, using few ms current sweeps of the laser, an accuracy of $> 0.02\text{‰}$ can be achieved in less than a minute. Thermal dependency of the absorption lines is also a very critical parameter. For achieving a precision of 0.02 ‰ on the isotopic signature the measurement cell would have to be stabilized at 1.5 mK. For this, we decided to make a mono-block aluminum double cell with two separate channels, one for the sample and one for the reference which will be measured simultaneously. This would allow gaining in immunity to thermal drifts, but not all of them, because thermal variation would induce both a change in the mechanics and therefore in the beam alignment as well as in the refractive index of the air, leading to the displacement of possible optical fringes on the spectrum, that would cause artifact in the measurement. A good thermal stabilization of the spectrometer is therefore still required and it is a critical point to achieve a good long-term stability (and therefore accuracy) of the measurement. A picture of the setup is reported in Figure 5.2. Each channel of the cell has a volume of 6 cm³, and requires only 3 g of ice in order to fill up the cell at 50 mbar of pressure. We minimized the amount of optics required on the setup in order to reduce as much as possible the scattering from the surface responsible of optical fringes on the signal. We acquired the two channels (sample and reference) using an acquisition card allowing for simultaneous detection. This allows to be less affected by common noise. An example of the spectra acquired is reported in Figure 5.3. The signal is characterized by the narrow ¹²CO₂ and ¹³CO₂ absorption lines at 50 mbar (for 400 ppm of CO₂ in air) with broader lines at atmospheric pressure underneath caused by the absorption of CO₂ while the beam is traveling outside the measurement cell. By adding soda lime inside the leak-tight optical box, those atmospheric absorption lines may be removed, allowing a better signal-to-noise ratio (because of the increase in intensity of the signal) as well as an easier spectral fit.

We put effort to linearize as best as possible the current saw-tooth ramp of the laser compensating for the chirp of the laser at the beginning of the scan. Each spectrum is acquired within 3.3 ms (300 Hz), and spectra are averaged 100 times before proceeding to the spectral fit. With this setup, we achieved a precision of 0.12‰ on the δ¹³CO₂ an ultimate 0.01‰ after 40 sec and 90 sec of acquisition, respectively. However, we did not put effort so far on the thermal stabilization the system, which lead to large long-term drifts which are strongly affecting the long-term accuracy of the system (see Figure 5.4). Further efforts to insulate and temperature-stabilize the optical spectrometer are ongoing, hoping to achieve better long-term stability of the system. Even if the measurement is already referenced to the standard gas injected in the second channel of the cell, we can still, from time

Figure 5.3: Example of the sample and reference spectra with 400 ppm of CO_2 at 50 mbar in the cell acquired at 300 Hz. The broader atmospheric absorption of CO_2 are visible underneath of the narrower absorption lines, and due to the absorption occurring while the laser is outside the measurement cell. This absorption is then removed (or at least minimized) by placing soda lime inside the spectrometer and making the optical box leak tight.

to time, inject the reference standard gas on the measurement channel to correct for experimental biases. Those biases are related to the fact that the laser beams going through the sample and reference channels have a different propagation path, therefore they experience different diffusion and scattering which are responsible for residual optical interferences.

This development started at the end of 2021 and was carried out by two engineers: E. Negre and F. Michel and the student Y. Yahiaoui. When finalize the thermal stabilization of the system, we will test the performance injecting different standard gas and validating its linearity for changes in isotopic signature as well as CO_2 concentrations. This work would then be published in a scientific journal.

5.3 Development of a new dry extraction method

Carbon dioxide, as Nitrous oxide (N_2O) are solubles in water. Therefore, if one wants to extract air bubbles for measuring those two species in past atmospheres, the well-known melting techniques cannot be used. For this reason, since few decades, different dry techniques have been developed by different research groups. A review of most of those techniques was presented in the PhD thesis of B. Bereiter, with a summary table in chapter 2, page 30 [Bereiter 2012]. The technique that provides

Figure 5.4: Left: An example of the measurement of $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ for about 2h, showing the presence of long-term drifts identified to be related to thermal instability. Right: the Allan-Werle statistical analysis on the same data set, showing the ultimate possible achievable precision of 0.01‰ after 1 min and 30 sec of acquisition (black curve) as well as the effect of long-term drift which at the moment strongly degrade the accuracy of the signal.

the highest efficiency for both air bubbles and clathrates is the sublimation, but at the price of a relatively complex setup and a slow extraction (current speed is 0.05 - 0.1 cm min^{-1}) [Mächler *et al.* 2023]. Clathrates are present in the deeper part of the ice core, below 500 - 1100 m of depth (depending on the site), where high-pressure and low-temperature conditions allow their formation. At IGE (formerly LGGE) in the 1980s, Robert Delmas was the pioneer to develop the ball mill technique for extracting the air bubbles in ice core [Delmas *et al.* 1980]. Since then, at IGE we have focused on this type of crushing technique, with further development of the ring mill system, which was largely tested during the PhD thesis of J. Shin [Shin 2019]. This system allows a better extraction efficiency but it has a very large dead volume (390 cm^3) which makes more difficult a direct injection into a spectrometer without having to use cryogenic trapping. Although at the beginning the contaminations in CO_2 were comparable to those of the ball mill system, they were getting worse and worse with the use of the ring mill cell, and the cover of the cell was showing marks due to the friction of the moving rings.

Regarding the extraction efficiency, the finer is the resulting ice powder the better will be the efficiency, and we would need powder $< 0.5 \text{ mm}$ for air bubbles to be extracted and much smaller for clathrates. Even if in Schaefer *et al.*, 2011 was reported an air extraction efficiency for the ball mill developed at IGE of 70 and 50% for bubbly and clathrate ice [Schaefer *et al.* 2011], we observed that only 23% of the ice has grain size $< 0.5\text{mm}$. For the ring system, the powder distribution is more interesting, with 64% of the ice $< 0.5 \text{ mm}$, but with the drawbacks mentioned above. The efficiency is less critical for bubbly ice, since would only cause a loss of air that would be analyzed but for ice within the bubble-clathrate transformation zone, where air bubbles and clathrate coexist, techniques with different efficiency may

not measure the same concentrations of CO₂ and as well possibly the same isotopic composition because during clathrate formation, the gas is partitioned between air bubble and clathrates depending on the different gas diffusivities and solubilities. Thus during clathrate formation, CO₂ has consistently been observed to be depleted in bubbles and enriched in clathrates, although, the physical processes responsible for this enrichment are still under debate [Schaefer *et al.* 2011].

Recent drilling projects are willing to find ice as old as 1.5 million years, such as the ongoing Beyond EPICA Oldest Ice (BE-OI) drilling at Little Dome C, at about 40 km from Concordia station, that reached a depth of 1836 meters in the last season (2023-24). Because of the age *vs* depth relationship, the layers are getting more and more thin while going deeper and we are expecting that at the bottom part, 10,000 year of history would be contained in only 1 m of ice core. If we want to maintain the 300-year resolution that we are currently achieving, we would need to do one measurement every 3 cm. The need of high resolution together with the fact that this oldest ice core will be unique and therefore very precious, push us to develop techniques that require less and less amount of ice, with a particular preference for multi-species analysis which allows to take the most out of each ice sample.

We therefore decided to develop a novel dry extraction method adapted to the optical spectrometer and described above. Here, the dead volume is an important parameter if we want to fill up the measurement cell at 50 mbar using a small amount of ice with a simple injection system (the ball mill system required 40g of ice, while current extraction techniques today aim to use only 10 g). Contamination of CO₂ should be minimized while the extraction efficiency maximized. Our idea is to use a vibrating mortar that crushes the ice sample by its own weight. The setup is reported in Figure 5.5, with the cell used for the test. The mortar is moving up and down with an excursion of 1 to 3 millimeters at a frequency of 50 Hz. As visible from Figure 5.5a the mortar is well fitted to the cell at the four edges of the cube, ensuring good vertical movement during the crushing and, due to a different radius of curvature between the internal volume of the cell and the mortar, the fine ice powder can be evacuated from the bottom of the cell through the interstitial volume. This technique should give less metal-to-metal friction and therefore less CO₂ out-gassing. We performed the first test using a small cell (30 ml dead volume) with a 40 × 40 mm (surface), 530g mortar. With this setup, we could crush ice with a good powder distribution (see Figure 5.6) for ice samples < 5g. For larger samples very large (>2mm) ice chips remained in the cell after crushing. Increasing the crushing time could not help to make finer powder. This indicates that the system reached a steady state with a mix of large ice chips surrounded by fine powder. The fine powder distributes around those large chips and acts as a dumper preventing the large chips from breaking off and the pressure exerted by the mortar is not enough anymore to break the residual larger ice chips. We then tested a larger cell (150 ml dead volume) with a larger and heavier mortar (90 × 90 mm surface, 1440g). With this second setup, we could nicely crush ice up to 20 g with a good powder distribution. The disadvantage of this cell is the large dead volume. Therefore, we wanted to test a third situation: we used the small cell with a heavy mortar

Figure 5.5: **a)** The smaller cell designed and constructed at IGE with a dead volume of 30 ml. **b)** the vibratory micro mill manufactured by Fritsch with at the top the larger crushing cell we developed (dead volume 150 ml); **c)** the ice powder resulting after crushing; **d)** a drawing of the cell, with the ice sample placed underneath the mortar.

(40 × 40 mm surface, 825g). This latest setup gave very good results, allowing to crush up to 10 g of ice with a good powder distribution (see Figure 5.6). Because of the small dead volume, we therefore validated this latest setup and we decided to manufacture the mortar with a Tungsten alloy which has a density twice the one of the stainless steel. With Tungsten we would reach a weight of the mortar of ~1 kg while maintaining the same design of the cell reported in Figure 5.5a and 5.5d. CO₂ out-gassing was also tested using the small cell made of stainless steel from both the cell and the mortar. CO₂ out-gassing was estimated to 1.5 - 2 ppm which is comparable with what we had with the ball mill system. It should be noticed that

the Tungsten alloy has 2 times less carbon than stainless steel ($<0.01\%$ of C vs $<0.02\%$ for the 316L), which should provide a further reduction of the out-gassing.

Figure 5.6: The powder distribution for the old ball mill system and of the vibrating mortar new method. Each of the curves was obtained by averaging data from a series of measurements.

This work, which is still ongoing, is carried on by the engineer G. Teste and the student Y. Yahiaoui. The cell designs were realized by R. Duphil from the technical service of IGE. We are now planning to validate the mortar made of Tungsten for both crushing efficiency and out-gassing. We then would have twelve cells manufactured, two of them to be used for blank tests conducted before and after a batch of ten measurements. This would allow us to gain time, and because of the simple gas injection strategy, and the fast time required by the optical spectrometer to reach precision $<0.02\%$ (few min), the ten measurements could be carried out in half-day.

In 10 g of ice we would have $\sim 1 \text{ cm}^3$ of air. This is an approximation since we should take into account the ice density, the air content which varies depending on the ice sample, and the extraction efficiency of the crushing method. If we want to directly expand this air sample from the crushing cell into the measurement cell, we would have about 50 cm^3 of total volume and we would reach a pressure of only 20 mbar. This direct expansion is simple, but not the best option because: i) most of the air sample remains in the crushing cell and is not used; ii) our spectrometer would have a better precision if we could reach a higher pressure of ~ 50 mbar. For this reason, we decided to develop a variable volume injection well adapted to our needs. We tried to do it using a glass syringe, but we had difficulties to reach the required vacuum leak tightness. We therefore decided to make the variable volume with a stainless-steel bellow. The one we acquired is custom-made in order

Figure 5.7: A schematic of the sample injection setup. The air sample present in the crushing cell will be expanded into a variable volume made of stainless steel bellow and then efficiently injected into the measurement cell by reducing the variable volume. The latter will also be used to adjust the pressure inside the measurement cell, and make it equal to the one of the reference cell.

to have a minimum volume ($< 10 \text{ cm}^3$) while the bellow is entirely compressed and a volume six times larger than the dead volume of the crushing cell when open (180 cm^3). A schematic of the injection part is reported in Figure 5.7. With this setup, we can expand the air sample from the crushing cell into the open bellow. Isolate the crushing cell, and compress the bellow to push the sample into the 6 cm^3 measurement cell. Because of the volume ratio, more than 80% of the air sample will be recovered in the bellow, and pushed into the cell, allowing to reach up to 80 mbar in the measurement cell with a 10 g ice core sample. This would allow to have enough amount of air even for samples with low air content and to take the most out of the ice sample.

5.4 Conclusion and perspectives

The system described in the previous two sections for measuring CO_2 and $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ in ice core is today still under development. The crushing method has been validated in terms of crushing efficiency and out-gassing, and the crushing cells will be manufactured shortly. The development of the optical spectrometer is also well-advanced. We reached the required precision within only few minutes of acquisition time, which matches our objectives. We are currently working on the long-term stability for maintaining the precision over longer measurement times. For this, we first try to remove the residual fringes but those seem to be generated by the diffused lights and it is difficult to remove them any further. At the moment we perform laser scans at 300 Hz, and by averaging them 100 times we reach a sensitivity on the measured transmission of 5×10^{-5} , which corresponds to a minimum absorption coefficient of $1.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and a figure of merit of $7.2 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1/2}$ or $1.3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ Hz}^{-1/2}$ per spectral elements (3000 in our case) [Grilli *et al.* 2012a],

which is a good achievement for a direct absorption technique within an optical path of only 40 cm. Better long-term stability will be obtained by thermal stabilizing the instrument. We are currently working on a three-stage thermal stabilization, with a PID (Proportional–integral–derivative) control for the measurement cell, one for the optical breadboard and last a peltier exchanger for the entire optical spectrometer. In parallel to this, we are finalizing the sample injection which should be ready soon allowing us to test the long-term stability and the linearity of the spectrometer by injecting the standard gas samples at different concentrations and isotopic signatures. The following step will be to couple the laser spectrometer with the extraction system, for conducting blank tests with synthetic ice. We aim to start measuring real ice core samples at the beginning of 2025, beginning with EPICA Dome C ice core samples from termination TII (~ 130 kyr B. P.).

In the frame of the ERC DOC-PAST "Deciphering the Oxidizing Capacity of the Past Atmosphere" led by J. Savarino we recently started the development of a new spectrometer for measuring the $\Delta^{17}\text{CO}$ anomaly (or ^{17}O -excess = $\delta^{17}\text{O} - 0.52 \times \delta^{18}\text{O}$), which is a proxy for retrieving the past oxidative capacity of the atmosphere. The oxidative capacity of the atmosphere is largely determined by the concentration and reactivity of OH radicals, which are the primary oxidants in the troposphere, and OH radicals play a crucial role in the oxidation of CO and other trace gases. Because atmospheric CO is oxidized to CO_2 by reaction with OH radicals, the rate of this reaction (which depends on the amount of OH present in the atmosphere) would affect the $\Delta^{17}\text{O}$ signature of CO. The spectrometer is based on the VCOF-CRDS technique already mentioned above and developed by S. Kassi at LIPhy [Stoltmann *et al.* 2017]. This high-sensitive technique consists in producing an ultra-narrow (few kHz) laser source by locking the laser to an ultra-stable V-shaped optical resonator. Then the laser is passed through a Mach-Zehnder Modulator (MZM) to remove the carrier envelope frequency and produce a single sideband source that can be tuned using a radiofrequency generator and injected into a second high-finesse resonator for CRDS measurements. This allows achieving the required spectral resolution independently from the geometry of the V-shaped cavity used (which is rather small to provide optimal mechanical stability). This technique has several advantages because it profits from an ultra-narrow laser source as the OFCEAS technique described previously in Chapter 3, and the immunity to amplitude noise of the CRDS technique. In the telecom range, where we can find the best high-reflective mirrors and where laser sources, optics and electro-optics components offers optimal performance, the VCOF-CRDS reaches state-of-the-art detection limits of $5 \times 10^{-13} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which corresponds to an absorption of the light of only 2 % on the path from Earth to the moon! This of course at the price of a more complex setup with respect to the other absorption methods and cavity-based techniques. This development was expected to be done at $2.39 \mu\text{m}$ region, where CO absorption lines are stronger than in the telecommunication wavelength region, but we faced at a technological limitation on the fabrication of the MZM module. Therefore we decided to go back to the $1.6 \mu\text{m}$ region. At this wavelength and accounting for the amount of gas available (discussed just below), the ^{17}CO and ^{18}CO

lines will be detected with a SNR of 1000 and 30000 respectively, allowing ‰ and sub-‰ precision. To achieve such a precision, we would also need an absolute frequency measurement, to place the probing laser exactly at a specific frequency. And because we know very well the physical parameters describing each absorption line, we can considerably reduce the number of measurement points for each absorption line, which reduces measurement time and increases the long-term accuracy of the instrument. Furthermore, the high precision on the frequency scale would reflect in a high precision on the absorption axes (because in spectroscopy, frequency noise converts into amplitude noise). LIPhy is part of the Refimeve (Réseau de Fibre Métrologique à Vocation Européenne) project and through it obtained and utilized absolute ultra-stable frequency signals (with a precision on the order of 10^{16} - 10^{18}) generated from atomic clocks at Paris Observatory. We are currently asking to have an optical fiber to link IGE and LIPhy laboratories and transfer this absolute optical frequency to IGE. The instrument is currently under development by L. Richard at LIPhy under the supervision of S. Kassi. In this project, I have a role at the interface to follow this development, make sure that it is advancing well, and that the final development will be adapted to our needs. The development will still take one more year before being installed at IGE. Afterward, we will work on the ice core analysis. Gas samples will be collected during this austral summer 2024/2025 at Concordia station. For each sample, 120 Kg of ice will be melted, giving ~ 12 L of air, which with an atmospheric concentration of ~ 50 ppb of CO makes ~ 27 nmol of CO available for the analysis.

General conclusion and perspectives

Contents

6.1 Strategy, objective, and feasibility	75
6.2 Research plan	79

I knew from the beginning that it would not be easy to be at the interface between two disciplines. With this manuscript, I wanted to highlight the advantages of such a position in geosciences and earth sciences applications, but also the difficulties I faced in trying to stay at this interface without getting too deep in fundamental physical developments or focusing too strongly on the applications. The advantages are very clear to me: a collaboration between a physics laboratory and a geosciences laboratory can lead to new developments and exciting projects. Physicists have an interest in proving that a tool they have developed works in real environments, so they often make the effort to go to real-condition deployments. But once this is done, and if the results are good, geoscientists are often willing to continue the deployment and obtain more of these new and exceptional data, while the physicists who developed the instruments need to go back to fundamental studies. Now, if the development has reached a maturity that allows a non-expert to operate it, then this is fine because a geoscientist can continue to do science with this new instrument. But if the tool still requires special expertise, then there is a risk that it will be left aside and no longer be used. Another advantage that I see is that a new tool can be designed and built for a particular application from the beginning, taking into account the performance required and the particular constraint of the possible deployments. Having the expertise in such an instrumental development internally in the geoscience laboratories is therefore a real added value, allowing new cutting-edge developments at the services of the geosciences.

6.1 Strategy, objective, and feasibility

In the last ten years of research, I conducted four main developments, meaning a new development every two or three years thanks to the help of seven engineers, two PhD students, eight undergraduate students, and the technical services at IGE. In Figure 6.1 I reported the temporality of these developments, knowing that all

Figure 6.1: Instrumental developments conducted during the last ten years. Usually, the first one or two years are purely dedicated to the development, and the following ones are for testing the instrument in the laboratory and in different environments and making science with it.

the instruments are at the moment still functioning. The SubOcean, the first development after the ones conducted during my two postdocs, is still performing field campaigns, the latest was in [Vietnam in June 2024](#) for mapping the dissolved gases in Vietnamien's rivers, following the land-to-sea continuum and documenting the formation, transport, and transformation of the greenhouse gases in this area. The two IBB-CEAS instruments are also on their way to the sub-Antarctic islands for a field campaign in October/November 2024 on board the research vessel Marion Dufresne and on Amsterdam Island. The main direction and objective for my research did not change from the one I had in mind at the time I got the position. Optical instrumentation has enormous potential for high-precision isotope ratio measurements, and this is the direction I would like to take for ice core science and dissolved gas detection. For atmospheric chemistry and ice core, I do not see the need to keep developing instrumentation for measuring the concentration of standard non-reactive species. This is now done relatively well and with high precision by several commercial instruments (Picarro, LGR, AP2E, Li-Cor, Aeris, Teledyne, Aerodyne Research, Tiger Optics, Axetris, Vaisale, Olythe, etc). But, among them, only a few are developing instruments for isotopic ratio measurements, and instruments for in situ isotopic measurement are very rare if not inexistent (LGR was proposing an instrument for in situ measurement of dissolved CH_4 and $\delta^{13}\text{CH}_4$, similar to the SubOcean that we developed, but as far as I know there were no sales of it). So, for ice-core science the direction I want to maintain is in the development of laboratory spectrometers for isotopic ratio measurements of CO_2 , CO , CH_4 , N_2O , O_2 , etc. The CO_2 development is advancing well and we are planning to start the measurement in real ice core by the beginning of 2025. The first measurements will be done on Termination II (120 - 130 kyr B.P.) occurring between the MIS5 and MIS6, of which previous measurements are available [[Eggleston et al. 2016](#)]. This would be a good opportunity to compare the quality of the data before moving to the other terminations and older periods for which data are not available yet. While for the atmospheric CO_2 measurements in ice cores we now have high-resolution (~ 300 years) measures over most of the first 430 kyr B.P. (MIS11), $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ records are only up to 160 kyr B.P.. There is therefore still a lot of effort to be made. The period going from 600 to 800 kyr B.P. has also a lot of interest and is the subject of the PhD thesis of Heloise Guilluy in our group. This part is conducted in collaboration

with the LSCE in Paris, the University of Bern in Switzerland, and the BAS in UK. Regarding further development, in the short term, we will advance on the VCOF-

Figure 6.2: A compilation of existing $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ measurements of atmospheric CO_2 covering the first 160 kyr B.P. (up to MIS6), together with other important proxies, including atmospheric CO_2 concentrations and temperature proxies ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and δD). From [Eggleston *et al.* 2016]

CRDS instrument for measuring the $\Delta^{17}\text{C}$ anomaly in ice core. It will take another year or two before we can perform routine measurements at the IGE. Afterward, the direction would probably be pointing toward the isotopic ratio measurement of CH_4 and N_2O . The VCOF-CRDS is a technique that, although more complex and bulky than other standard CEAS and CRDS techniques, has unprecedented performance, and in the last few years, efforts for miniaturization and simplification have been made. Having access at the Refimeve's ultra-stable frequency signals at IGE will allow cutting-edge metrological developments in the future, which are essential for accurate absorption measurements.

In situ, precise, fast and compact dissolved gas sensor work are still not easily available. What is limiting the response time is the gas extraction system. With the SubOcean we managed to considerably reduce it (from 40 min to 30 sec) but with an increase in complexity of the instrument which then limits what can be done in terms of miniaturization and power consumption. For this reason, in the following years I would like to work on a new generation of instruments for which the gas is no longer extracted and the measurement occurs as close as possible to the liquid interphase. As explained in Chapter 3 this can be done by evanescent wave detection. Even if the first attempt to get funding for this project did not succeed, I am planning to ask for other funding because I strongly believe in the potential of this approach. For existing sensors, the SubOcean will continue to be used in ongoing projects (Terra Forma and CarboNium), with the aim of reducing the application of our laboratory prototype over time and encouraging scientists to acquire the commercial instrument. Regarding the SWIS instrument, there is still a lot of science to do with this new tool. We had more technical problems than expected with this development because of the challenge of reaching very high accuracy for *in situ* isotopic measurements. But we are on a good track and we are confident that the instrument will operate properly after a few more improvements (such as the improvement of the mechanical stability of the optical system that I mentioned in Chapter 3 and the heating of the gas line between the reference membrane and the measurement cell to avoid condensation that has already been integrated). Field campaign opportunities for the SWIS instrument would arise in the following year. In the short term, we may have a possibility to join a cruise in the Arctic organized by the colleagues at LOCEAN, and a funding application was submitted in June 2024 for starting a new collaboration with colleagues from the University of St. Andrews, with possible field campaigns in the Arctic and Antarctica.

In atmospheric chemistry, I would keep the main focus on the detection of reactive species. I think that there is still a strong need for reliable measurements of molecules such as the hydroxyl and peroxy radicals (OH, HO₂, RO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO, NO₂ and NO₃) halogenated molecules (XO, and OXO, with X = I, Br, Cl). Our attempt to measure BrO and IO in a close cavity proved to suffer from loss of radicals in the sampling line, we are therefore putting our efforts for making measurements either in an open-cavity system or in a LP-DOAS configuration. The open-cavity IBB-CEAS measurements were proven last summer with the internship of F. Pastierovic and it would be tested in the ML-CEAS system as well for the detection of the OH radical in the HELIOS chamber in Orleans in collaboration with Veronique Daële and Max McGillen from ICARE. This project should start in September 2024, with the hiring of 1-year engineer to start the development, followed by a PhD student scholarship that would allow us to validate the development and prove the first applications of the spectrometer for atmospheric chemistry applications. New developments on the LP-DOAS approach are also ongoing with the ANR project RADICALS (2024 - 2028) led by D. Romanini and with the joint effort between the IPR in Rennes, LIPHy, and IGE in developing novel LP-DOAS

approaches using broad-band coherent light.

It is not easy to maintain the instruments we have already developed, keeping them up to date, improving and deploying them, while at the same time continuing to propose new developments. This requires a growing number of engineers, as is already the case (Figure 6.3). To keep up with the rate of development I am currently proposing, different strategies are needed:

- Find a good compromise between field and laboratory instrumentation. Field instruments had further constrain of having people to operate in the field, which can be sometimes under difficult and extreme conditions. The development of spectrometers for laboratory measurements would enable them to be implemented on existing analytical platforms (such as PANDA for ice core analysis) which have a team of technicians and engineers who can be trained to use the new tools.
- Developments must always be brought to a point where a non-expert user can use them. This allows, for example, geoscientist colleagues to use an instrument in the field. This is already the case with the SubOcean and IBB-CEAS developments, and it should always be the case for future developments.
- When possible, explore the possibility to go for a technological transfer toward a company to make the instruments commercially available for the community or a laboratory so that they can be duplicated and broadly used. This is the very last step of achievement, it may take a while before reaching this point (for the SubOcean it tooks eight years!) but once is done, it would allow to spare time to develop new generation of sensors.
- Last but not least, having a permanent engineer with expertise in optical instrumentation would help to follow the developments, do the maintenance, train the users, and deploy the instruments in the field.

6.2 Research plan

On the different projects, I am the leader every time instrumental development is the main part of the project, and I am co-PI or partner of projects where the main focus is on the geoscience applications. For PhD supervision so far I supervised one student for each research axis. A part from the one of A. Wohleber, that focused primarily on instrumental development, the other two were co-supervised by colleagues with expertise in geoscientific applications. I found this way of working very nice and productive, particularly if the PhD subject has a good balance between instrumental development/optimization and the earth science application. The PhD of A. Barbero was a perfect example of a successful PhD work at the interface between the two disciplines, with two field campaigns in Antarctica and three scientific publications (one instrumental and two on the applications). I also try to have a good

Figure 6.3: Follow up of the non-permanent staff that I supervised since I obtained the research position in October 2015.

balance between engineers, PhD students, and Master students that I am supervising, In Table 6.1 I reported plans for the coming five years of research. This planning tempts to find a good equilibrium between new instrumental developments, laboratory validations, and geoscientific applications. For the research activity on aquatic systems, now that the SubOcean instrument went into a technological transfer, in the following years I am planning to move into a new generation of dissolved gas sensors based on evanescent wave detection. With the existing SubOcean instrument, in collaboration with the company A2 Photonic Sensors we will implement the direct absorption measurement of the dissolved CO_2 and $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ to the existing spectrometer. This can be done by sending the mid-IR laser at $4.3 \mu\text{m}$ to the resonant cavity at $3.3 \mu\text{m}$, but the current coating of the high-reflective mirrors is too broad and the transmission at $4.3 \mu\text{m}$ would unfortunately be too poor. This would then require asking for a new mirror coating or we could add a second measurement cell dedicated to the CO_2 measurement. The electronic card of the spectrometer is already equipped to have a second laser and it the software already has the option to perform alternated measurements between two lasers. What would need to be implemented in the software is the analysis of the direct absorption system, but it has already be done for the laboratory spectrometer for ice core application, so its implementation should be relatively easy. Regarding the Evanescent wave development I am looking for a grant and I hope that this development could start beginning of 2026. For the SWIS instrument, I look forward to the publication of our work to *Limnology and Oceanography: Methods* journal. After the field campaign in Fimbulshen Ice Shelf we already conducted some improvements on the

robustness of the instrument. These improvements need to be finalized and would be conducted in the frame of the Horizon Europe project OCEAN:ICE for which I still have six months of engineer contract to propose. J. Witwicky is starting a PhD in our group but on a different topic, therefore I will look for another engineer to finalize this work, and a potential candidate would be A. Wohleber once his PhD will be finished. Afterward, we may would have an opportunity thorough a UK application we submitted in June 2024 with colleagues from the University of St Andrews to have field test opportunities. The SWIS instrument needs first to be validated on board of research vessel or platforms, before being deployed again underneath an ice shelf. If these "easy-deployment" tests are successful, the next step would be to lead an ambitious high-gain high-risk project for installing those instruments through boreholes in strategic locations over a summer season to capture the temporal variability of the melting signal. I would like to see this SWIS development going through technological transfer towards a company to duplicate this unique tool and make it more widely available to the scientific community working on the freshwater cycle and ice shelf - ocean interactions. On the atmospheric chemistry

		2025	2026	2027	2028	2029
Water	SubOcean instrument :					
	Dissolved CO ₂ and δ ¹³ CO ₂					
	SubOcean probe deployments					
	New Evanescent Wave System :					
	Development of a new system for dissolved GHGs					
	Test of the instrument					
Measurement campaigns						
SWIS instrument:						
Improvements and validation						
Measurement campaigns						
Atmosphere	IBBCEAS instruments :					
	Campaign at DDU					
	New open path IBBCEAS for BrO detection at 340 nm					
	Other field campaigns					
	ML-CEAS instrument for OH detection :					
	Development					
	Tests and validation					
	Applications at HELIOS atmospheric chamber					
LP-DOAS approach :						
Tests of LIPhy's and IRP's developments						
Applications						
Ice	CO₂ and δ¹³CO₂ meausurement :					
	Validation on synthetic ice					
	Validation on TII ice core					
	Adding δ ¹⁵ N ₂ O measurements					
	Applications in ice core					
	Δ¹⁷CO measurements :					
	Development VCOF-CRDS for Δ ¹⁷ CO measurements					
Validation on standard gas						
Installation at IGE and ice core measurements						

Table 6.1: Gantt chart with my research plan for the following five years

axes, we are going to deploy the IBB-CEAS instruments at Amsterdam Island in the coming Austral summer. We still do not know what to expect in terms of level

of NO_x , IO since there are not measurements in the literature at this location. So, it is a very exploratory field campaign. We are planning then to deploy the instruments at Dumont D'Urville (DDU) station, on the East coast of Antarctica. Here, NO_2 measurements were performed by us in 2012-2013 [Grilli *et al.* 2013] and NO levels were deduced from steady-state calculation using the measurement of OH performed during the OPALÉ campaign. It could be very interesting to perform again the measurement of IO this time with the open-path IBB-CEAS instrument, and adding direct measurement of NO using the OFCEAS instrument. This campaign could be done in the frame of a new PhD work, where the student could do the field campaign and work on the comparison between the data collected at the three different locations (at DC in the Antarctic plateau, 75°S, at DDU on the coast, 66°S, and at Amsterdam Island, 35°S). The development of the ML-CEAS for the detection of the OH radical is ready to start. We purchased most of the equipment, and we are willing to hire an engineer in September-October 2025 who will develop the system in Grenoble under my supervision. Afterward, we are willing to apply for a PhD scholarship between Grenoble and Orelans to validate the development, conduct the installation at the HELIOS chamber, and conduct the first measurements for atmospheric chemistry applications. Regarding the LP-DOAS technique, the development is led by the LIPhy and the IPR. My role is mainly to conduct the first tests in Grenoble and programming further applications in the field. In Grenoble, we installed a corner cube (retro-reflector) at the Fort Saint Eynard that can be pointed from our laboratory at IGE allowing 10 km back-and-forward path length. We also have an optical setup allowing us to superpose the laser beam to an alignment green laser and a visible camera mounted on a $\times 25$ telescope, and an automatized routine for searching the alignment to the corner cube.

Last but not least, in the ice cores research axes in 2025 I am planning to finalize the development of the CO_2 and $\delta^{13}\text{CO}_2$ measurement setup with test and validation of the technique with standard gas, synthetic ice, and ice core sample from termination II. This would be done by the engineer G. Teste with the help of a work-study student Y. Yahiaoui who would have a half-time contract for the next three years to work on the optical developments for ice-core applications. The measurements on ice core samples will then be performed by PhD students in our group working on the carbon cycle (H. Guilluy is in her first year of PhD, and will be the first student to benefit from this development). To take the most out of the extracted air sample, an OF-CEAS spectrometer for measuring N_2O and $\delta^{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}$ could be added to the setup. This optical spectrometer is already available at LIPhy and provides ppb detection limit for N_2O and an accuracy of 0.2‰ on the $\delta^{15}\text{N}_2\text{O}$. The development of the VCOF-CRDS instrument for measuring the $\Delta^{17}\text{CO}$ anomaly in ice core will be finalized and installed at IGE in 2025. We would then perform the validation of the measurements using standard gases followed by the analysis of the samples acquired in the frame of the DOC-PAST project for retrieving the oxidative capacity of the past atmosphere.

Bibliography

- [Akhoudas *et al.* 2020] Camille Akhoudas, Jean-baptiste Sallée, Gilles Reverdin, Giovanni Aloisi, Marion Benetti, Lucie Vignes and Maria Gelado. *Ice Shelf Basal Melt and Influence on Dense Water Outflow in the Southern Weddell Sea*. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans*, vol. 125, no. 2, pages 1–19, feb 2020. (Cited on page 37.)
- [Albertin *et al.* 2024] Sarah Albertin, Joël Savarino, Slimane Bekki, Albane Barbero, Roberto Grilli, Quentin Fournier, Irène Ventrillard, Nicolas Caillon and Kathy Law. *Diurnal variations in oxygen and nitrogen isotopes of atmospheric nitrogen dioxide and nitrate: implications for tracing NO_x oxidation pathways and emission sources*. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 24, no. 2, pages 1361–1388, jan 2024. (Cited on page 53.)
- [Barbero *et al.* 2020] Albane Barbero, Camille Blouzon, Joël Savarino, Nicolas Caillon, Aurélien Dommergue and Roberto Grilli. *A compact incoherent broadband cavity-enhanced absorption spectrometer for trace detection of nitrogen oxides, iodine oxide and glyoxal at levels below parts per billion for field applications*. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, vol. 13, no. 8, pages 4317–4331, aug 2020. (Cited on pages 45, 46 and 53.)
- [Barbero *et al.* 2021] A. Barbero, J. Savarino, R. Grilli, C. Blouzon, G. Picard, M. M. Frey, Y Huang and N. Caillon. *New Estimation of the NO_x Snow-Source on the Antarctic Plateau*. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 126, no. 20, oct 2021. (Cited on pages 46, 47 and 49.)
- [Barbero *et al.* 2022] Albane Barbero, Roberto Grilli, Markus M. Frey, Camille Blouzon, Detlev Helmig, Nicolas Caillon and Joël Savarino. *Summer variability of the atmospheric NO₂ : NO ratio at Dome C on the East Antarctic Plateau*. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 22, no. 18, pages 12025–12054, sep 2022. (Cited on pages 49, 51 and 52.)
- [Bärenbold *et al.* 2020] Fabian Bärenbold, Bertram Boehrer, Roberto Grilli, Ange Mugisha, Wolf von Tümpling, Augusta Umutoni and Martin Schmid. *No increasing risk of a limnic eruption at Lake Kivu: Intercomparison study reveals gas concentrations close to steady state*. *PLOS ONE*, vol. 15, no. 8, page e0237836, aug 2020. (Cited on pages 29 and 32.)
- [Bereiter *et al.* 2020] Bernhard Bereiter, Béla Tuzson, Philipp Scheidegger, André Kupferschmid, Herbert Looser, Lars Mächler, Daniel Baggenstos, Jochen Schmitt, Hubertus Fischer and Lukas Emmenegger. *High-precision laser spectrometer for multiple greenhouse gas analysis in 1 mL air from ice core samples*. *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques*, vol. 13, no. 11, pages 6391–6406, nov 2020. (Cited on page 64.)

- [Bereiter 2012] Bernhard Bereiter. *No Title*. PhD thesis, University of Bern, 2012. (Cited on page 66.)
- [Bernhardt *et al.* 2010] Birgitta Bernhardt, Akira Ozawa, Patrick Jacquet, Marion Jacquey, Yohei Kobayashi, Nathalie Picque, Thomas Udem, Ronald Holzwarth, Guy Guelachvili and Theodor W Ha. *Cavity-enhanced dual-comb spectroscopy*. *Nature Photonics*, vol. 4, no. November 2009, pages 2009–2011, 2010. (Cited on page 22.)
- [Bigg & Rohling 2000] G.; Bigg and E.; Rohling. *An oxygen isotope data set for marine waters*. *Geophysical Research*, vol. 105, no. C4, pages 8527–8535, 2000. (Cited on page 35.)
- [Bock *et al.* 2016] Josué Bock, Joël Savarin and Ghislain Picard. *Air-snow exchange of nitrate: A modelling approach to investigate physicochemical processes in surface snow at Dome C, Antarctica*. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 16, no. 19, pages 12531–12550, 2016. (Cited on page 48.)
- [Boulart *et al.* 2008] Cédric Boulart, Matthew C Mowlem, Douglas P Connelly, Jean-pierre Dutasta and Christopher R German. *A novel , low-cost , high performance dissolved methane sensor for aqueous environments*. vol. 16, no. 17, pages 41–51, 2008. (Cited on page 26.)
- [Brown *et al.* 2014] Peter J. Brown, Michael P. Meredith, Loïc Jullion, Alberto Naveira Garabato, Sinhue Torres-Valdés, Paul Holland, Melanie J. Leng and Hugh Venables. *Freshwater fluxes in the Weddell gyre: Results from $\delta 18 O$* . *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, vol. 372, no. 2019, 2014. (Cited on page 35.)
- [Burkholder *et al.* 2004] J. B. Burkholder, J. Curtius, A. R. Ravishankara and E. R. Lovejoy. *Laboratory studies of the homogeneous nucleation of iodine oxides*. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, vol. ', pages 19–34, 2004. (Cited on page 44.)
- [Carlson *et al.* 2018] David R Carlson, Daniel D Hickstein, Daniel C Cole, Scott A Diddams and Scott B Papp. *Dual-comb interferometry via repetition-rate switching of a single frequency comb*. *Optics Letters*, vol. 43, pages 3614–3617, 2018. (Cited on page 59.)
- [Chan *et al.* 2018] Hoi Ga Chan, Markus M Frey and Martin D King. *Modelling the physical multiphase interactions of HNO_3 between snow and air on the Antarctic Plateau (Dome C) and coast (Halley)*. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, vol. 18, pages 1507–1534, 2018. (Cited on page 48.)
- [Chua *et al.* 2016] Emily J. Chua, William Savidge, R. Timothy Short, Andres M. Cardenas-Valencia and Robinson W. Fulweiler. *A review of the emerging*

- field of underwater mass spectrometry*. *Frontiers in Marine Science*, vol. 3, no. NOV, pages 1–24, 2016. (Cited on page 26.)
- [Craig & Gordon 1965] H Craig and L I Gordon. *Stable Isotopes in Oceanographic Studies and paleotemperatures*. 1965. (Cited on page 35.)
- [Davis *et al.* 2008] Douglas D Davis, Jon Seelig, Greg Huey, Jim Crawford, Gao Chen, Yuhang Wang, Marty Buhr, Detlev Helmig, William Neff, Don Blake, Rich Arimoto and Fred Eisele. *A reassessment of Antarctic plateau reactive nitrogen based on ANTCI 2003 airborne and ground based measurements*. *Atmospheric Environment*, vol. 42, pages 2831–2848, 2008. (Cited on page 48.)
- [DeConto & Pollard 2016] Robert M. DeConto and David Pollard. *Contribution of Antarctica to past and future sea-level rise*. *Nature*, vol. 531, no. 7596, pages 591–597, 2016. (Cited on page 43.)
- [Delmas *et al.* 1980] R.J. Delmas, J.-M. Ascencio and M. Legrand. *Polar ice evidence that atmospheric CO₂ 20,000 yr BP was 50present*. *Nature*, vol. 284, no. 155, 1980. (Cited on page 67.)
- [Dølven *et al.* 2022] Knut Ola Dølven, Juha Vierinen, Roberto Grilli, Jack Triest and Bénédicte Ferré. *Response time correction of slow-response sensor data by deconvolution of the growth-law equation*. *Geoscientific Instrumentation, Methods and Data Systems*, vol. 11, no. 2, pages 293–306, aug 2022. (Cited on page 31.)
- [Dullo *et al.* 2015] Firehun Tsige Dullo, Susan Lindecrantz, J Jana, Jørn H Hansen, Magnus Engqvist, Stian Andre Solbø and Gaute Helleø. *Sensitive on-chip methane detection with a cryptophane-A cladded Mach-Zehnder interferometer*. vol. 23, no. 24, pages 477–480, 2015. (Cited on page 26.)
- [Dyroff *et al.* 2010] C. Dyroff, D. Fütterer and A. Zahn. *Compact diode-laser spectrometer ISOWAT for highly sensitive airborne measurements of water-isotope ratios*. *Applied Physics B*, vol. 98, no. 2-3, pages 537–548, feb 2010. (Cited on page 36.)
- [Eggleston *et al.* 2016] S. Eggleston, J. Schmitt, B. Bereiter, R. Schneider and H. Fischer. *Evolution of the stable carbon isotope composition of atmospheric CO₂ over the last glacial cycle*. *Paleoceanography*, vol. 31, no. 3, pages 434–452, mar 2016. (Cited on pages 76 and 77.)
- [Foltynowicz *et al.* 2011] Aleksandra Foltynowicz, Ticijana Ban, Piotr Masłowski, Florian Adler and Jun Ye. *Quantum-Noise-Limited Optical Frequency Comb Spectroscopy*. *Physical Review Letters*, vol. 233002, no. December, pages 1–5, 2011. (Cited on page 22.)
- [Frew *et al.* 2000] Russell D Frew, Paul F Dennis, Karen J Heywood, Michael P Meredith and Steven M Boswell. *The oxygen isotope composition of water*

- masses in the northern North Atlantic*. Deep-Sea Research I, vol. 47, pages 2265–2286, 2000. (Cited on page 35.)
- [Frey *et al.* 2015] M. M. Frey, H. K. Roscoe, A. Kukui, J. Savarino, J. L. France, M. D. King, M. Legrand and S. Preunkert. *Atmospheric nitrogen oxides (NO and NO₂) at Dome C, East Antarctica, during the OPALE campaign*. Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics, vol. 15, no. 14, pages 7859–7875, jul 2015. (Cited on page 52.)
- [Fuchs *et al.* 2009] Hendrik Fuchs, William P. Dubé, Brian M. Lerner, Nicholas L Wagner, Eric J. Williams and Steven S. Brown. *A Sensitive and Versatile Detector for Atmospheric NO₂ and NO_x Based on Blue Diode Laser Cavity Ring-Down Spectroscopy*. Environmental Science and Technology, vol. 43, no. 20, pages 7831–7836, oct 2009. (Cited on page 45.)
- [Gourmelen *et al.* 2017] Noel Gourmelen, Dan N. Goldberg, Kate Snow, Sian F. Henley, Robert G. Bingham, Satoshi Kimura, Anna E. Hogg, Andrew Shepherd, Jeremie Mouginot, Jan T.M. Lenaerts, Stefan R.M. Ligtenberg and Willem Jan van de Berg. *Channelized Melting Drives Thinning Under a Rapidly Melting Antarctic Ice Shelf*. Geophysical Research Letters, vol. 44, no. 19, pages 9796–9804, 2017. (Cited on page 36.)
- [Graf *et al.* 2018] Manuel Graf, Lukas Emmenegger and Béla Tuzson. *Compact, circular, and optically stable multipass cell for mobile laser absorption spectroscopy*. Optics Letters, vol. 43, no. 11, page 2434, 2018. (Cited on page 19.)
- [Graves *et al.* 2015] Carolyn A. Graves, Lea Steinle, Gregor Rehder, Helge Niemann, Douglas P. Connelly, David Lowry, Rebecca E. Fisher, Andrew W. Stott, Heiko Sahling and Rachael H. James. *Fluxes and fate of dissolved methane released at the seafloor at the landward limit of the gas hydrate stability zone offshore western Svalbard*. Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans, vol. 120, no. 9, pages 6185–6201, sep 2015. (Cited on page 30.)
- [Grilli *et al.* 2012a] R Grilli, C Abd Alrahman, I Ventrillard, S Kassi and D Romanini. *Cavity-enhanced multiplexed comb spectroscopy down to the photon shot noise*. Physical Review A, vol. 051804, pages 1–5, 2012. (Cited on pages 22 and 71.)
- [Grilli *et al.* 2012b] Roberto Grilli, Guillaume Mejean, Samir Kassi, Chadi Abdalrahman and Daniele Romanini. *Frequency Comb Based Spectrometer for in Situ and Real Time Measurements of IO, BrO, NO₂, and H₂CO at pptv and ppqv Levels*. Environmental Science and Technology, vol. 46, no. 2, page 1070410710, 2012. (Cited on pages 45, 55 and 56.)
- [Grilli *et al.* 2013] Roberto Grilli, Michel Legrand, Alexandre Kukui, Guillaume Méjean, Suzanne Preunkert and Daniele Romanini. *First investigations of IO, BrO, and NO₂ summer atmospheric levels at a coastal East Antarctic*

- site using mode-locked cavity enhanced absorption spectroscopy*. *Geophysical Research Letters*, vol. 40, no. 4, pages 791–796, 2013. (Cited on pages 45 and 82.)
- [Grilli *et al.* 2018] Roberto Grilli, Jack Triest, Jérôme Chappellaz, Michel Calzas, Thibault Desbois, Pär Jansson, Christophe Guillerm, Bénédicte Ferré, Loïc Lechevallier, Victor Ledoux and Daniele Romanini. *Sub-Ocean: Subsea Dissolved Methane Measurements Using an Embedded Laser Spectrometer Technology*. *Environmental Science and Technology*, vol. 52, no. 18, pages 10543–10551, 2018. (Cited on page 29.)
- [Grilli *et al.* 2020] Roberto Grilli, François Darchambeau, Jérôme Chappellaz, Ange Mugisha, Jack Triest and Augusta Umutoni. *Continuous in situ measurement of dissolved methane in Lake Kivu using a membrane inlet laser spectrometer*. *Geoscientific Instrumentation, Methods and Data Systems*, vol. 9, no. 1, pages 141–151, apr 2020. (Cited on pages 29 and 32.)
- [Grilli *et al.* 2021] Roberto Grilli, Dominique Birot, Mia Schumacher, Jean-Daniel Paris, Camille Blouzon, Jean Pierre Donval, Vivien Guyader, Helene Leau, Thomas Giunta, Marc Delmotte, Vlad Radulescu, Sorin Balan, Jens Greinert and Livio Ruffine. *Inter-Comparison of the Spatial Distribution of Methane in the Water Column From Seafloor Emissions at Two Sites in the Western Black Sea Using a Multi-Technique Approach*. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, vol. 9, jul 2021. (Cited on pages 29 and 32.)
- [Grilli *et al.* 2023] R Grilli, T. DelSontro, J Garnier, F Jacob and J. Némery. *A Novel High-Resolution In Situ Tool for Studying Carbon Biogeochemical Processes in Aquatic Systems: The Lake Aiguebelette Case Study*. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences*, vol. 128, no. 12, dec 2023. (Cited on pages 29, 32 and 33.)
- [Helmig *et al.* 2020] Detlev Helmig, Daniel Liptzin, Jacques Hueber and Joel Savarino. *Impact of exhaust emissions on chemical snowpack composition at Concordia Station , Antarctica*. *The Cryosphere*, vol. 14, pages 199–209, 2020. (Cited on pages 48 and 52.)
- [Hönninger *et al.* 2004] G Hönninger, C Von Friedeburg and U Platt. *Multi axis differential optical absorption spectroscopy (MAX-DOAS)*. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, vol. 4, no. 1, page 2316é(?), 2004. (Cited on page 44.)
- [Ideguchi *et al.* 2014] Takuro Ideguchi, Antonin Poisson, Guy Guelachvili, Nathalie Picqué and Theodor W. Hänsch. *Adaptive real-time dual-comb spectroscopy*. *Nature communications*, vol. 5, page 3375, 2014. (Cited on page 22.)
- [Jansson *et al.* 2019] Pär Jansson, Jack Triest, Roberto Grilli, Bénédicte Ferré, Anna Silyakova, Jürgen Mienert and Jérôme Chappellaz. *High-resolution underwater laser spectrometer sensing provides new insights into methane*

- distribution at an Arctic seepage site.* Ocean Science, vol. 15, no. 4, pages 1055–1069, aug 2019. (Cited on page 29.)
- [Jones *et al.* 2001] A. E. Jones, R. Weller, P. S. Anderson, H. W. Jacobi, E. W. Wolff, O. Schrems and H. Miller. *Measurements of NO_x emissions from the Antarctic snowpack.* Geophysical Research Letters, vol. 28, no. 8, pages 1499–1502, 2001. (Cited on page 44.)
- [Kerstel 2004] Erik Kerstel. *Isotope Ratio Infrared Spectrometry.* Handbook of Stable Isotope Analytical Techniques, pages 759–787, 2004. (Cited on page 36.)
- [Kukui *et al.* 2014] A Kukui, M Legrand, S Preunkert, M M Frey, R Loisil, J Gil Roca, B Jourdain, M D King and Université Pierre. *Measurements of OH and RO₂ radicals at Dome C , East Antarctica.* pages 12373–12392, 2014. (Cited on pages 44 and 50.)
- [Lhomme *et al.* 2005] Nicolas Lhomme, Garry K.C. Clarke and Catherine Ritz. *Global budget of water isotopes inferred from polar ice sheets.* Geophysical Research Letters, vol. 32, no. 20, pages 1–4, 2005. (Cited on page 35.)
- [Liang *et al.* 2019] Shuaxi Liang, Min Qin, Pinhua Xie, Jun Duan, Wu Fang, Yabai He, Jin Xu, Jingwei Liu, Xin Li, Ke Tang, Fanhao Meng, Kaidi Ye, Jianguo Liu and Wenqing Liu. *Development of an incoherent broadband cavity-enhanced absorption spectrometer for measurements of ambient glyoxal and NO₂ in a polluted urban environment.* Atmospheric Measurement Techniques, vol. 12, no. 4, pages 2499–2512, apr 2019. (Cited on page 45.)
- [Mächler *et al.* 2012] Lars Mächler, Matthias S. Brennwald and Rolf Kipfer. *Membrane inlet mass spectrometer for the quasi-continuous on-site analysis of dissolved gases in groundwater.* Environmental Science and Technology, vol. 46, no. 15, pages 8288–8296, 2012. (Cited on page 26.)
- [Mächler *et al.* 2023] Lars Mächler, Daniel Baggenstos, Florian Krauss, Jochen Schmitt, Bernhard Bereiter, Remo Walther, Christoph Reinhard, Béla Tuzson, Lukas Emmenegger and Hubertus Fischer. *Laser-induced sublimation extraction for centimeter-resolution multi-species greenhouse gas analysis on ice cores.* Atmos. Meas. Tech., pages 355–372, 2023. (Cited on page 67.)
- [Makarov 2000] Alexander Makarov. *Electrostatic axially harmonic orbital trapping: A high-performance technique of mass analysis.* Analytical Chemistry, vol. 72, no. 6, pages 1156–1162, 2000. (Cited on page 26.)
- [Meusinger *et al.* 2014] Carl Meusinger, Tesfaye A. Berhanu, Joseph Erbland, Joel Savarino and Matthew S. Johnson. *Laboratory study of nitrate photolysis in Antarctic snow. I. Observed quantum yield, domain of photolysis, and secondary chemistry.* Journal of Chemical Physics, vol. 140, no. 24, 2014. (Cited on page 48.)

- [Min *et al.* 2016] K Min, R A Washenfelder, W P Dubé, A O Langford, P M Edwards, K J Zarzana and J Stutz. *A broadband cavity enhanced absorption spectrometer for aircraft measurements of glyoxal, methylglyoxal, nitrous acid, nitrogen dioxide, and water vapor*. vol. 5, no. 2, pages 423–440, 2016. (Cited on pages 45 and 58.)
- [Morville *et al.* 2005] J. Morville, S. Kassi, M. Chenevier and D. Romanini. *Fast, low-noise, mode-by-mode, cavity-enhanced absorption spectroscopy by diode-laser self-locking*. Applied Physics B: Lasers and Optics, vol. 80, no. 8, pages 1027–1038, 2005. (Cited on pages 21 and 29.)
- [Morville *et al.* 2014] Jérôme Morville, Daniele Romanini and Erik Kerstel. *Cavity-Enhanced Spectroscopy and Sensing with Optical Feedback*. In Gianluca Gagliardi and Hans-Peter Loock, editors, Cavity-Enhanced Spectroscopy and Sensing, Springer Series in Optical Sciences. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2014. (Cited on pages 21 and 29.)
- [Muto *et al.* 2011] Atsuhiko Muto, Ted A. Scambos, Konrad Steffen, Andrew G. Slater and Gary D. Clow. *Recent surface temperature trends in the interior of East Antarctica from borehole firn temperature measurements and geophysical inverse methods*. Geophysical Research Letters, vol. 38, no. 15, pages 6–11, 2011. (Cited on page 43.)
- [Nasse *et al.* 2019] Jan-marcus Nasse, Philipp G Eger, Denis Pöhler, Stefan Schmitt, Udo Friß and Ulrich Platt. *Recent improvements of long-path DOAS measurements: impact on accuracy and stability of short-term and automated long-term observations*. Atmospheric Measurement Techniques, vol. 12, no. 8, pages 4149–4169, aug 2019. (Cited on page 44.)
- [Navas *et al.* 1997] M.J. Navas, A.M. Jiménez and G. Galán. *Air analysis: determination of nitrogen compounds by chemiluminescence*. Atmospheric Environment, vol. 31, no. 21, pages 3603–3608, 1997. (Cited on page 44.)
- [Nehrbass-Ahles *et al.* 2020] C. Nehrbass-Ahles, J. Shin, J. Schmitt, B. Bereiter, F. Joos, A. Schilt, L. Schmidely, L. Silva, G. Teste, R. Grilli, J. Chappellaz, D. Hodell, H. Fischer and T. F. Stocker. *Abrupt CO₂ release to the atmosphere under glacial and early interglacial climate conditions*. Science, vol. 369, no. 6506, pages 1000–1005, 2020. (Cited on page 61.)
- [Padman *et al.* 2018] Laurie Padman, Matthew R. Siegfried and Helen A. Fricker. *Ocean Tide Influences on the Antarctic and Greenland Ice Sheets*. Reviews of Geophysics, vol. 56, no. 1, pages 142–184, 2018. (Cited on page 36.)
- [Richard *et al.* 2018] Lucile Richard, Daniele Romanini and Irène Ventrillard. *Nitric oxide analysis down to ppt levels by optical-feedback cavity-enhanced absorption spectroscopy*. Sensors (Switzerland), vol. 18, no. 7, 2018. (Cited on pages 45, 53 and 58.)

- [Rintoul *et al.* 2016] Stephen Rich Rintoul, Alessandro Silvano, Beatriz Pena-Molino, Esmee Van Wijk, Mark Rosenberg, Jamin Stevens Greenbaum and Donald D. Blankenship. *Ocean heat drives rapid basal melt of the totten ice shelf*. *Science Advances*, vol. 2, no. 12, pages 1–6, 2016. (Cited on page 36.)
- [Romanini *et al.* 2014] Daniele Romanini, Irène Ventrillard, Guillaume Méjean, Jérôme Morville and Erik Kerstel. *Introduction to Cavity Enhanced Absorption Spectroscopy*. In Gianluca Gagliardi and Hans-Peter Loock, editors, *Cavity-Enhanced Spectroscopy and Sensing*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2014. (Cited on page 19.)
- [Rutkowski *et al.* 2018] Lucile Rutkowski, Piotr Masłowski, Alexandra C Johansson, Amir Khodabakhsh and Aleksandra Foltynowicz. *Optical frequency comb Fourier transform spectroscopy with sub-nominal resolution and precision beyond the Voigt profile*. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy Radiative Transfer*, vol. 204, pages 63–73, 2018. (Cited on page 59.)
- [Ryerson *et al.* 2000] T. B. Ryerson, E. J. Williams and F. C. Fehsenfeld. *An efficient photolysis system for fast-response NO₂ measurements*. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, vol. 105, no. D21, pages 26447–26461, nov 2000. (Cited on page 44.)
- [Saunois *et al.* 2019] Marielle Saunois, Ann R. Stavert, Ben Poulter, Philippe Bousquet, Joseph G. Canadell, Robert B. Jackson, Peter A. Raymond, Edward J. Dlugokencky, Sander Houweling, Prabir K. Patra, Philippe Ciais, Vivek K. Arora, David Bastviken, Peter Bergamaschi, Donald R. Blake, Gordon Brailsford, Lori Bruhwiler, Kimberly M. Carlson, Mark Carrol, Simona Castaldi, Naveen Chandra, Cyril Crevoisier, Patrick M. Crill, Kristofer Covey, Charles L. Curry, Giuseppe Etiope, Christian Frankenberg, Nicola Gedney, Michaela I. Hegglin, Lena Höglund-Isakson, Gustaf Hugelius, Misa Ishizawa, Akihiko Ito, Greet Janssens-Maenhout, Katherine M. Jensen, Fortunat Joos, Thomas Kleinen, Paul B. Krummel, Ray L. Langenfelds, Goulven G. Laruelle, Licheng Liu, Toshinobu Machida, Shamil Maksyutov, Kyle C. McDonald, Joe McNorton, Paul A. Miller, Joe R. Melton, Isamu Morino, Jureck Müller, Fabiola Murgia-Flores, Vaishali Naik, Yosuke Niwa, Sergio Noce, Simon O’Doherty, Robert J. Parker, Changhui Peng, Shushi Peng, Glen P. Peters, Catherine Prigent, Ronald Prinn, Michel Ramonet, Pierre Regnier, William J. Riley, Judith A. Rosentreter, Arjo Segers, Isobel J. Simpson, Hao Shi, Steven J. Smith, Paul L. Steele, Brett F. Thornton, Hanqin Tian, Yasunori Tohjima, Francesco N. Tubiello, Aki Tsuruta, Nicolas Viovy, Apostolos Voulgarakis, Thomas S. Weber, Michiel van Weele, Guido R. van der Werf, Ray F. Weiss, Doug Worthy, Debra Wunch, Yi Yin, Yukio Yoshida, Wenxin Zhang, Zhen Zhang, Yuanhong Zhao, Bo Zheng, Qing Zhu, Qiuan Zhu and Qianlai Zhuang. *The Global Methane Budget 2000-2017*. *Earth System Science Data*, vol. 12, no. 3, pages 1561–1623, aug 2019. (Cited on page 25.)

- [Schaefer *et al.* 2011] Hinrich Schaefer, Anna Laurantou, Jérôme Chappellaz, Dieter Lüthi, Bernhard Bereiter and Jean-marc Barnola. *On the suitability of partially clathrated ice for analysis of concentration and $\delta^{13}C$ of palaeo-atmospheric CO₂*. Earth and Planetary Science Letters, vol. 307, no. 3-4, pages 334–340, 2011. (Cited on pages 67 and 68.)
- [Schmid *et al.* 2019] Martin Schmid, Fabian Bärenbold, Bertram Boehrer, Roberto Grilli and Jack Triest. *Intercalibration Campaign for Gas Concentration Measurements in Lake Kivu*. no. January 2019, 2019. (Cited on page 32.)
- [Shin *et al.* 2020] Jinhwa Shin, Christoph Nehrbass-Ahles, Roberto Grilli, Jai Chowdhry Beeman, Frédéric Parrenin, Grégory Teste, Amaelle Landais, Loïc Schmidely, Lucas Silva, Jochen Schmitt, Bernhard Bereiter, Thomas F. Stocker, Hubertus Fischer and Jérôme Chappellaz. *Millennial-scale atmospheric CO₂ variations during the Marine Isotope Stage 6 period (190–135 ka)*. Climate of the Past, vol. 16, no. 6, pages 2203–2219, nov 2020. (Cited on pages 61 and 62.)
- [Shin 2019] Jinhwa Shin. *Millennial-scale atmospheric CO₂ variations during the Marine Isotope Stage 6*. PhD thesis, 2019. (Cited on page 67.)
- [Stoltmann *et al.* 2017] Tim Stoltmann, Mathieu Casado, Mathieu Daëron, Amaelle Landais and Samir Kassi. *Direct, Precise Measurements of Isotopologue Abundance Ratios in CO₂ Using Molecular Absorption Spectroscopy: Application to $\Delta^{17}O$* . Analytical Chemistry, vol. 89, no. 19, pages 10129–10132, 2017. (Cited on pages 21, 63 and 72.)
- [Thomason & Peter 2006] L Thomason and T Peter. *Assessment of stratospheric aerosol properties (ASAP)*. Report of the 9 th Session of the . . . , no. 1295, page 348, 2006. (Cited on page 43.)
- [Tortell 2005] Philippe D. Tortell. *Dissolved gas measurements in oceanic waters made by membrane inlet mass spectrometry*. Limnology and Oceanography: Methods, vol. 3, no. 1, pages 24–37, 2005. (Cited on page 26.)
- [Tran *et al.* 2013] H Tran, N H Ngo and J Hartmann. *Efficient computation of some speed-dependent isolated line profiles*. Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer, vol. 129, pages 199–203, 2013. (Cited on page 18.)
- [Walker *et al.* 2016] S. A. Walker, K. Azetsu-Scott, C. Normandeau, D. E. Kelley, R. Friedrich, R. Newton, P. Schlosser, J. L. McKay, W. Abdi, E. Kerrigan, S. E. Craig and D. W.R. Wallace. *Oxygen isotope measurements of seawater ($H^{218}O/H^{216}O$): A comparison of cavity ring-down spectroscopy (CRDS) and isotope ratio mass spectrometry (IRMS)*. Limnology and Oceanography: Methods, vol. 14, no. 1, pages 31–38, 2016. (Cited on page 36.)
- [Wittrock *et al.* 2004] F. Wittrock, H. Oetjen, A. Richter, S. Fietkau, T. Medeke, A. Rozanov and J. P. Burrows. *MAX-DOAS measurements of atmospheric*

- trace gases in Ny-Ålesund- Radiative transfer studies and their application.* Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics, vol. 4, no. 4, pages 955–966, 2004. (Cited on page 44.)
- [Wolff *et al.* 2006] E. W. Wolff, H. Fischer, F. Fundel, U. Ruth, B. Twarloh, G. C. Littot, R. Mulvaney, R. Röthlisberger, M. De Angelis, C. F. Boutron, M. Hansson, U. Jonsell, M. A. Hutterli, F. Lambert, P. Kaufmann, B. Stauffer, T. F. Stocker, J. P. Steffensen, M. Bigler, M. L. Siggaard-Andersen, R. Udisti, S. Becagli, E. Castellano, M. Severi, D. Wagenbach, C. Barbante, P. Gabrielli and V. Gaspari. *Southern Ocean sea-ice extent, productivity and iron flux over the past eight glacial cycles.* Nature, vol. 440, no. 7083, pages 491–496, 2006. (Cited on page 43.)
- [Zhang & Cloud 2006] Haibing Zhang and Andy Cloud. *The permeability characteristics of silicone rubble.* International SAMPE Technical Conference, 2006. (Cited on page 28.)
- [Zhang *et al.* 2017] Xin Zhang, Zengfeng Du, Ronger Zheng, Zhendong Luan, Fujun Qi and Kai Cheng. *Deep – Sea Research I Development of a new deep-sea hybrid Raman insertion probe and its application to the geochemistry of hydrothermal vent and cold seep fluids.* Deep-Sea Research Part I, vol. 123, no. February, pages 1–12, 2017. (Cited on page 26.)
- [Zhu *et al.* 2008] Chengzhu Zhu, Bin Xiang, Lei Zhu and Richard Cole. *Determination of absorption cross sections of surface-adsorbed HNO₃ in the 290 – 330 nm region by Brewster angle cavity ring-down spectroscopy.* Chemical Physics Letters, vol. 458, pages 373–377, 2008. (Cited on page 49.)